

CRITICAL CHANGE LAB

Deliverable D4.1

Communication Plan

Project Title	Democracy meets arts: critical change labs for building democratic cultures through creative and narrative practices
Grant Agreement No.	101094217
Project Acronym	Critical ChangeLab
EC Call	HORIZON-CL2-2022-DEMOCRACY-01-04
Work Package	WP4 Communicate Disseminate Exploit
Work Package Leaders	ALTEREURO
Deliverable Lead Beneficiary	5. AE
Contractual Delivery Date Version 1	31.08.2023
Actual Delivery Date Version 1	08.09.2023
Actual Delivery Date Revised Version	04.10.2024
Delayed	Yes
Nature	R — Document, report
Dissemination Level	PU - Public
Partner(s) contributing to this deliverable	AE, ALTEREURO
Authors	Andrew Newman (AE) Ana-Maria Carabelea (AE)
Contributors	Niccolo Milanese (ALTEREURO) Jacc Griff (ALTEREURO)
Acknowledgments	None
Reviewers	Heidi Hartikainen (OULU) Johanna Lenhart (AE) Vanessa Hanneschläger (AE)

Revision History

Date	No.	Who	Description
31.07.2023	0.1	Andrew Newman (AE)	Draft submitted for internal review by Waag, Kersnikova, University of Oulu
18.08.2023	0.2	Andrew Newman (AE)	Revised draft incorporating suggestions and changes from reviews from Eva Vesseur (Waag) Tamar ter Steege (Waag) Eva Durall Gazulla (UOULU) Andreja Lapuh (KERSNIKOVA) submitted for internal review by Veronika Liebl (AE)
23.08.2023	0.3	Andrew Newman (AE)	Revised Draft submitted for internal review by Eva Durall Gazulla (UOULU)
31.08.2023	0.9	Andrew Newman (AE)	Final draft submitted to Coordinator for final review.
08.09.2023	1.0	Andrew Newman (AE)	Final version incorporating all revisions and feedback.
30.09.2024	2.0	Ana-Maria Carabelea (AE)	Revised version following review meeting.

Disclaimer: Critical ChangeLab is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101094217. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

Revision History	3
Table of Contents.....	4
Index of Tables	7
Glossary	8
Executive Summary	9
1. Introduction.....	10
1.1 About Critical ChangeLab	10
1.2 Scope of deliverable.....	10
1.3 Context of deliverable within WP4.....	12
1.3.1. About WP4: COMMUNICATE, DISSEMINATE AND EXPLOIT	12
1.3.2 Related tasks within WP4.....	12
1.4 Relationship of deliverable to other work packages.....	14
1.5 Structure of deliverable.....	15
2. Objectives.....	16
2.1 Background	16
2.2 Project Objectives	17
2.3 Communication Objectives.....	18
2.3.1 Activate Engagement	19
2.3.2 Facilitate Dialogue	19
2.3.3 Demonstrate Impact.....	19
2.3.4 Advocate Change.....	20
2.3.5 Multiply Knowledge	20
2.4 Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Targets.....	21
2.4.1 Communication Targets	21
2.4.2 Dissemination Targets	22
2.4.3 Exploitation Targets.....	23
3. Channels.....	24
3.1 Defining Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Channels	24
3.2 Communication Channels.....	26
3.2.1 Visual Identity.....	26

3.2.2 Project Website.....	27
3.2.3 Social media.....	28
3.2.4 Newsletter	28
3.2.5 Video.....	29
3.2.6 Press releases.....	29
3.3 Dissemination Channels.....	29
3.3.1 Critical ChangeLabs.....	29
3.3.2 Teacher education and professional development actions.....	30
3.3.3 Direct outreach.....	31
3.3.4 Conference presentations, seminars, expert panels and civil society moments.....	32
3.3.5 Project-led conferences	32
3.3.6 Workshops and focus groups.....	32
3.3.7 Academic journals, book publications and conference papers.....	34
3.3.8 Publication of Open Data.....	34
3.4 Exploitation Channels	35
3.4.1 Critical ChangeLabs	35
3.4.2 Youth Mentorship Program.....	35
3.4.3 Youth Assembly	36
3.4.4 Critical ChangeLab Resource Library.....	36
3.4.5 Critical ChangeLab MOOC.....	36
3.4.6 Policy Publications.....	37
4. Target Groups	37
4.1 Target Group 1: Researchers and research institutions.....	38
4.1.1 Audience profile of TG1.....	38
4.1.2 Relationship of TG1 to Critical ChangeLab.....	39
4.1.3 Key messages for reaching TG1.....	40
4.1.4 Channels used for reaching TG1.....	40
4.2 Target Group 2: Formal and non-formal education professionals.....	41
4.2.1 Audience profile of TG2	41
4.2.2 Relationship of TG2 to Critical ChangeLab & Objectives.....	42
4.2.3 Key messages & channels for reaching TG2.....	43
4.2.4 Channels used for reaching TG2.....	44
4.3 Target Group 3: Young people, their families and the general public	45
4.3.1 Audience profile of TG3	45
4.3.2 Relationship of TG3 to Critical ChangeLab & Objectives.....	46
4.3.3 Key messages & channels for reaching target group.....	46
4.3.4 Channels used for reaching TG3.....	48

4.4 Target Group 4: Civil society organisations and industry	48
4.4.1 Audience profile of TG4	48
4.4.2 Relationship of TG4 to Critical ChangeLab & Objectives	49
4.4.3 Key messages & channels for reaching TG4	50
4.4.4 Channels used for reaching TG4	51
4.5 Target Group 5: Policy and decision makers	51
4.5.1 Audience profile of TG5	51
4.5.2 Relationship of TG5 to Critical ChangeLab & Objectives	52
4.5.3 Key messages & channels for reaching TG5	53
4.5.4 Channels used for reaching TG4	53
5. Action Plan and Workflow	54
5.1 Coordinating Communication	54
5.2 Communication Code-of-Conduct	54
5.3 Accessible design guidelines	55
6. Monitoring and Evaluation	56
7. Conclusion	57
8. References	59
9. Annexes	61
Annex 1: Critical ChangeLab Visual Identity	61
Annex 2: Critical ChangeLab Code of Conduct	61
Annex 3: Possible Communication Campaigns	61

Index of Tables

Table 1: Dissemination Workflow	11
Table 2: Overview of WP4 Deliverables	13
Table 3: Deliverable Structure	15
Table 4: Outline of Communication Objectives	18
Table 5: Overview of Communication KPIs	21
Table 6: Overview of Exploitation KPIs	22
Table 7: Overview of Exploitation KPIs	23
Table 8: Outline of the 5 Audience Target Groups of Critical ChangeLab	38
Table 9: Audience profile of Target Group 1 (TG1)	38
Table 10: Audience profile of Target Group 2 (TG2)	41
Table 11: Audience profile of Target Group 3 (TG3)	45
Table 12: Audience profile of Target Group 4 (TG4)	48
Table 13: Audience profile of Target Group 5 (TG5)	51

Glossary

CO	Communication Objective
Critical ChangeLab	Democracy meets arts: Critical change labs for building democratic cultures through creative and narrative practices
CSO	Civil Society Organisation
D	Deliverable
DEC	Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.
DHI	Democracy Health Index
DHQ	Democracy Health Questionnaire
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
Ethics AB	Ethics Advisory Board
Expert AB	Expert Advisory Board
GA	General Assembly
IWG	Internal Working Group
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
MS	Milestone
NECE	Networking European Citizenship Education
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
PAR	Participatory Action Research
PMG	Project Management Group
PO	Project Officer
PU	Public
R	Document, Report
SEN	Sensitive
T	Task
TG	Target Group
WP	Work Package
YA	Youth Assembly

Executive Summary

Critical ChangeLab (Democracy Meets Arts: Critical Change Labs for Building Democratic Cultures through Creative and Narrative Practices) is a Horizon Europe research and innovation project addressing democratic erosion trends by strengthening youth participation in society. The project is carried out by 10 partner institutions and examines the current state of democracy in learning environments across Europe, generating a robust evidence base for the design of a participatory democratic curriculum. Critical ChangeLab develops a model of democratic pedagogy using creative and narrative practices to foster youth's active democratic citizenship at a time when polarisation and dwindling trust in democracy are spreading across Europe. At the Critical ChangeLabs, diverse actors from formal and non-formal education and civic organizations work together with youth to rethink European democracy and envision futures that are justice-oriented.

This deliverable outlines the Communication Plan that will be implemented within the Critical ChangeLab project and corresponds to *Task T4.1 Set-up communication guidelines & plan for consortium within WP4 Communicate Disseminate Exploit*.

The purpose of this document is to describe the communication, dissemination and exploitation plan to be adopted by Critical ChangeLab at different stages of the project and for different target groups. Its purpose is to formalise all communication, dissemination and exploitation actions by outlining a unified approach, and, thus, facilitate the dissemination of outcomes and results to ensure the long-term impact of the project and exploitation of its results.

Developed by AE in association with consortium partners, the plan elaborates on the Critical ChangeLab communication, dissemination and exploitation objectives, corresponding target audiences, key messages, communication tools and channels, as well as the monitoring and evaluation strategy.

This document is a revised version of the initial communication plan informed by the learnings from the first year of the project and the recommendations made by the project officer and reviewers following the first review meeting in M12. Moreover, the current version looks towards the needs of the second part of the project (different from those in the first year) and tries to respond to them with an updated, more targeted outreach strategy. In contrast to the first version, it shifts the focus from online campaigns and the KPIs associated with them and outlines a strategy to reach relevant target groups, focusing on the most appropriate channels and project outputs.

1. Introduction

1.1 About Critical ChangeLab

Critical ChangeLab (Democracy Meets Arts: Critical Change Labs for Building Democratic Cultures through Creative and Narrative Practices) is a Horizon Europe research and innovation project addressing democratic erosion trends by strengthening youth participation in society. The project is carried out by 10 partner institutions and embraces a transdisciplinary approach combining expertise from Arts and Humanities, Social Sciences, as well as Science and Technology.

Specifically, the Critical ChangeLab project develops a model of democratic pedagogy using creative and narrative practices to foster youth's active democratic citizenship at a time when polarisation and dwindling trust in democracy are spreading across Europe. The Critical ChangeLab Model for Democratic Pedagogy fosters learners' transformative agency and strengthens democratic processes in education through collaborations across formal and non-formal education and local actors around global/local challenges relevant for youth. The Model promotes creative and narrative practices to explore the historical roots of local and EU-wide challenges, understanding the value-systems and worldviews underlying distinct types of relations (human-human, human-nature, human-technology). At the Critical ChangeLabs, young people are introduced to approaches such as theatre of the oppressed, transmedia storytelling, as well as speculative and critical design to rethink European democracy and envision democracy futures that are justice oriented.

Throughout the project lifespan, the Critical ChangeLab project examines the current state of democracy within education institutions identifying youth's perspectives on everyday democracy; designing a scalable and tailorable model of democratic pedagogy in formal and non-formal learning environments; co-creating and implementing the model with youth and stakeholders; evaluating the model; generating recommendations for policy and practice; and developing strategies to sustain the model and its outcomes overtime.

The Critical ChangeLab project uses mixed model research design combining quantitative and in-depth qualitative research on democracy and youth with participatory action research cycles to generate a robust evidence base to support democratic curriculum development using participatory, creative, and critical approaches.

1.2 Scope of deliverable

This deliverable aims to provide an overview of the key objectives of the communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategy and how they will be reached, including core messages, target audiences, channels, and partner engagement levels.

These guidelines have been further enhanced by the creation of a Code of Conduct (Annex 2) that promotes fair, inclusive, and diverse communication practices within the consortium and beyond. The primary aim of this Code of Conduct is to reduce barriers to accessibility and outreach by addressing and bridging cultural, educational, economic, geographical, and social differences. The communication plan is a living document and will be

regularly updated to adapt to the development of the project. Departing from the initial communication plan, we do not detail the communication campaigns. Instead, this version shifts the focus from a general communication strategy to a more targeted one. In practical terms this means:

- A focus on the dissemination channels that can help us reach specific audiences with the exploitable outputs that are most relevant for them. This is especially relevant in the second part of the project, when most publications and research pieces will be made available online. This will be done by dividing the dissemination activities into three categories: policy, research, and training, corresponding to three of our main target groups.

Table 1: Dissemination Workflow

- In the above diagram, the updated approach to the Communications Plan divides the dissemination activities into three categories, positioning the communications category as central and intersecting, becoming a point of transaction between each dissemination category, as represented by each Internal Working Group (IWG) for Policy, Research and Training (IWG-P, IWG-R, and IWG-T, respectively). This means that the IWGs will focus on their respective category, feeding back information (publications, resources, etc.) that will be translated into communications materials by the central working group (Communication). Examples of dissemination activities that come under each category are diverse and may include: policy briefs, conferences and policy workshops (IWG-P); academic journal publications, round-table discussions and library resources (IWG-R); as well as a mentorship programme, MOOC (Massive Open Online Course) and educator's handbook (IWG-T).
- The role of the communication measures is to support the dissemination of exploitable results by building clear narratives around each of these outcomes, summarising how specific target audiences can/should use and benefit from them.

- An online campaign structure (including both social media posts and paid ads) dictated by the target group (inspired by, but not following the chronological order of the initial campaign outline in Annex 3). Instead, the structure of the Library section, where outcomes will be grouped according to target groups, will inform the digital communication campaigns, to make it easier for different target groups to access relevant resources.

As such, the chronological outline of the **online communication** campaigns (typically **less targeted**), is replaced by a map connecting objectives and relevant channels (communication, dissemination, exploitation), target audiences and outputs. This allows us to use channels better to direct research findings and other exploitable outputs and resources to their target audiences and ensure the project achieves its objectives and has a long-lasting impact. [OB]

The present version of the document replaces the updated version of the Communication Plan foreseen for M18. The adjustments to the initial version of the communication plan are based on learnings from the first year of the project and recommendations made by the reviewers and the project officer.

1.3 Context of deliverable within WP4

1.3.1. About WP4: COMMUNICATE, DISSEMINATE AND EXPLOIT

WP4 is led by ALTEREURO and is focused on communication, dissemination, and sustainability. It includes the development of the Critical ChangeLab website, communication measures, and the implementation of an active and inclusive outreach strategy. The goal is to sustain the project outcomes beyond its lifespan. The work package will create communication guidelines for all partners (e.g. visual identity manual, social media visuals and captions etc.), carry out **communication** activities, **disseminate** the project's outputs (in conferences, workshops, courses, etc.), and outline an **exploitation** strategy (focusing on the project outputs with the biggest long-term impact, such as the Massive Online Course (MOOC), for relevant stakeholders in education and culture at European and international levels).

The communication strategy will engage all partners in promoting the results and learnings of the project, seeking to give learners, educators, and direct beneficiaries a voice by designing and implementing an inclusive approach to communication and dissemination. By giving a voice to different stakeholders, we reiterate the importance of a democratic approach and strengthen the case made by the Critical ChangeLabs themselves. Moreover, this ensures a more extensive and credible dissemination effort that can better support the exploitation of the project results.

1.3.2 Related tasks within WP4

This deliverable is the outcome of T4.1 Set-up communication guidelines & plan for consortium that is led by Ars Electronica (AE). It establishes the plan for and is directly linked to T4.2 Implementation of communication activities. This deliverable additionally provides a general guide for the dissemination and exploitation activities that will be undertaken throughout other tasks in WP4 that are described below:

T4.3 Community empowerment activities for a sustained take up of methods

Task T4.3 takes place from M2 - M36 and is led by ALTEREURO and is focused on the exploitation activities of the project and ensuring the actual take-up for the project's results and deliverables through education and mentoring.

This part of the work package is specifically focused on reaching out to and empowering education professionals. Its goal is the adoption of our methods by educators in both formal and non-formal education institutions, and ultimately, its integration in the school curricula.

The communication strategy (led by AE) will support this task by formulating key messages to ensure consistent and coherent storytelling that narrates our work to different target groups and engages them to achieve maximum impact. Coherent storytelling is essential, especially when empowering others to take up our methods, as they will become the ambassadors of the model in the long run.

T4.4 Dissemination activities

Task T4.4 takes place from M2 - M36 and is led by ALTEREURO and is focused on delivering a range of dissemination events and activities to various groups. This includes partners' participation in dissemination activities consisting of conference presentations, seminars, and expert panels, policy-focused online roundtables, technology-focused online workshops with technology providers/developers, educators and researchers and two high impact events to showcase the project's outcomes to a larger audience of citizenship educators. The dissemination activities start at the beginning of the project to secure early interest and awareness of the project, notably amongst policy makers and technology stakeholders.

The communication strategy (led by AE) will support this task by formulating key messages to ensure consistent and coherent storytelling that narrates our work to different target groups and engages them to achieve maximum impact.

T4.5 Definition of implications for policy

Task 4.5 takes place from M12 – M36 is led by ALTEREURO and focuses on the exploitation and dissemination measures that can be undertaken within Critical ChangeLab to ensure the outputs of the project can have an impact on policy. The task will deliver policy briefs and reports targeting policy- and decision-makers in order to communicate the research implications of Critical ChangeLab for policy. A dialogue with interested policy-makers from as early in the project will ensure that policy recommendations are well targeted, pertinent and have a receptive audience.

The communication strategy (led by AE) will support this task by formulating key messages to ensure consistent and coherent storytelling that narrates our work to different target groups and engages them to achieve maximum impact.

The following table provides an overview of each deliverable within WP4 and the aspects that they will cover:

Table 2: Overview of WP4 Deliverables

No.	Deliverable	Est. Delivery	Partner	Specification
D4.1	Communication Plan	M5	AE	Communication plan
D4.2	Policy Brief 1	M12	ISRZ	Policy Brief 1 - based on outputs from WP1 (Map & Design), in particular on the reports D1.2 and D1.3.
D4.3	Critical ChangeLab MOOC	M23	ALTEREURO	Critical ChangeLab Model of Democratic Pedagogy MOOC
D4.4	Young leaders video campaign	M25	AE	Young leaders video campaign
D4.5	Policy Brief 2	M30	UB	Policy brief 2 - building on results from WP3 (Evaluate), D3.1, D3.2.
D4.6	Policy recommendations	M30	ALTEREURO	Policy recommendations on citizenship education for sustainable European democracy
D4.7	Communication and Dissemination Report	M36	AE	Report on all project communication and dissemination activities

1.4 Relationship of deliverable to other work packages

Communication and dissemination activities hold a unique position in relation to other tasks and work packages as they are interconnected with most other project activities. The Communication Plan for the Critical ChangeLab project is therefore closely interlinked with and shares interdependencies and relationships with effectively all outputs, work packages, deliverables, and activities within the project. In creating a strategy to communicate all these components, the communication plan plays a vital role in effectively disseminating outputs and engaging with key target groups and stakeholders.

For this reason, the objectives of the communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy are closely aligned with the distinct kinds of project outputs. Thus, the relationship between the measures outlined here and the different tasks and deliverables, depends on the nature of the task or deliverable, and can be summed up as below:

- Some tasks require **communication activities both before and after their completion** (e.g. Democracy Health Index (T1.1), the running of the three PAR cycles of the Critical ChangeLabs (T1.4, T2.2, T2.3)). The activities will be directed both towards **activating participant engagement** in the project and **facilitating dialogue** with the participants, as well as towards communicating the results/outcomes of the tasks to education professionals and policy-makers to **advocate change and multiply knowledge**.
- The publication of research results (e.g. D1.1 – Instrument: Democracy Health Questionnaire and Index, D1.2 – Everyday democracy in formal and non-formal education institutions, D1.3 – Youth perspectives on everyday democracy, D1.4 – Critical ChangeLab Model: Framework and Toolkit, D2.3 – Critical ChangeLab Educators’ Handbook, D3.1 – Critical ChangeLab process and recommendations for practice, D3.2 – Critical ChangeLab Model for Democratic Pedagogy: Developing 21st Century Skills for Democratic Participation, D3.3 – Critical ChangeLab impact evaluation, D3.4 – Policy recommendations

based on the socio-economic evaluation of the Critical ChangeLab Model) will require **communication and dissemination after completion**. Here, the role of WP4 will be to formulate the key messages that **demonstrate the impact** of the outputs and support the **multiplication of knowledge** among target audiences. In this case, the timeline of the communication activities must follow the timeline according to which tasks and deliverables are completed. Therefore, any delays in the other work packages will cause delays to the implementation of the communication plan.

- In other cases, the **communication strategy will support the dissemination of exploitable and actionable outputs** (e.g. D4.2 Policy Brief 1, D4.3 Critical ChangeLab Model of Democratic Pedagogy MOOC, D4.5 Policy Brief 2, D4.6 Policy recommendations on citizenship education for sustainable European democracy, T2.4/D2.3 Development of the Critical ChangeLab Educator’s Handbook) by formulating unified messages to **advocate change**. The dissemination and exploitation activities will be carried out by ALTEREURO, however the narratives around the different project outcomes will be developed in collaboration with AE (both for the online communication channels, as well as for the dissemination and exploitation channels) to ensure a consistent way of communicating across all partners and channels.

In the project’s first year we have built the credibility needed for the dissemination of outputs in the second half of the project. This was done by introducing the project and the partners, as well as by engaging participants and facilitating a dialogue that allowed their feedback and participation in the design of the model. This has created a solid base on which we can rely to demonstrate the impact of our work, advocate for change, and increase the adoption and exploitation of our model.

1.5 Structure of deliverable

The Communication Plan starts by outlining the broader goals of the project and how the communication objectives will help achieve these goals. It further details the channels (communication, dissemination, and exploitation) we plan to use before discussing audience profiles. When describing the audiences, we draw the connections between each target group and the project’s objectives, establishing the most relevant channels for each target group. Thus, the current deliverable builds a comprehensive profile of all audience groups - by aligning the general objectives, available channels, and resources and tools it will develop - to create a more effective, targeted outreach plan.

Table 3: Deliverable Structure

2. Objectives

2.1 Background

A disconcerting disconnection between liberalism and democracy is creating the perception of a crisis of democracy in Europe. Despite this rise of ‘illiberal democracy’ or ‘undemocratic liberalism’ (Mounk, 2018), surveys continue to demonstrate that Europeans remain both supportive of democratic values (Reynié, 2019; IDEA, 2021) and democratic systems of government (Wuttke, Gavras, & Schoen, 2022). Furthermore, the future of democracy in Europe appears to be bright, evidenced by young Europeans strong ongoing support for democracy (Zilinsky, 2019). It appears, at least within Europe, that fears of a democratic deconsolidation brought upon by young people disengagement with democracy (Foa & Mounk, 2017) are unfounded. Even so, while studies may show democracy as a concept is highly valued in Europe, there appears to be increasing discord in how that concept is understood (Kirsch & Welzel, 2019), how the concept is measured (König, Siewert & Ackermann, 2022) and what actively participating in this concept even entails (Checkoway, 2011; Escobar, 2017; Warren, 2002).

Such semantic ambiguity surrounding abstract values and concepts can posit an openness and inclusivity that invites us to actively participate in shared and negotiated meaning-making. Yet this ‘post-truth’ era in which we now find ourselves can also invite misuse, abuse, and manipulation (van Dyk, 2022) from illiberal actors who ‘behave like Humpty Dumpty in Lewis Carroll’s *Through the Looking Glass*’, emboldened by a realisation that ‘these values can mean whatever they choose them to mean’ (Mos, 2020). Ambiguity is further amplified through increasing misinformation caused by corrupted media systems (Surowiec & Štětka, 2020) and accelerated by digital technologies (Cosention, 2020). The greatest threat to democracy is not only the idea that it is *unassailable* (Carey et al., 2019), but also the idea that it is *immutable*.

Warnings of an erosion of democracy and shrinking European civic space should therefore not go unheeded. Democratic politics is under siege, but the assault is often being framed under the guise of democracy itself (Krastev and Holmes, 2019; Runciman, 2018). To counter such *misdefinition* and its corresponding *misinformation*, a capacity for critical thinking needs to be encouraged, that approaches such ambiguity not as something to be exploited and instrumentalized, but as an invitation for open participation.

Communication for a project on democracy and education is vital to the project itself. Clarity of communication is crucial to countering misinformation, and it essential that a communication plan remains open adopting an approach that's respectful and responsive to the voices of those participating and engaging with the project. This document therefore is not prescriptive nor definitive but is designed to create the impetus for dialogue with all participating partners through a living document.

2.2 Project Objectives

The main goal of the Critical Change Lab is to contribute to building a resilient European democracy by reinvigorating the relationship between youth and democracy through civic interventions in which young people can envision alternative futures for (shared) European democracy and are empowered to act on that. The project aims to principally achieve this with the development and delivery of a flexible Critical ChangeLab Model of Democratic Pedagogy. A broader framework of seven specific objectives is defined within the project to ensure Critical ChangeLab can achieve this goal.

- 01. EXAMINE** the current state of democracy within education institutions and **IDENTIFY** youth's perspectives on everyday democracy.
- 02. DESIGN** a scalable and tailorable model Critical ChangeLab Model of Democratic Pedagogy for supporting democratic transformations in formal and non-formal learning environments
- 03. CO-CREATE** and **IMPLEMENT** the Critical ChangeLab Model in collaboration with stakeholders.
- 04. EVALUATE** the Critical ChangeLab Model process, impact, and socio-economic cost.
- 05. SUSTAIN** the Critical ChangeLab activities beyond the Critical ChangeLab project lifespan
- 06. SHARE** and **EXPLOIT** the Critical ChangeLab project outputs.
- 07.** Create a **ROBUST EVIDENCE BASE** to support democratic curriculum development.

2.3 Communication Objectives

It is important to ensure that the objectives of the Communication Plan for Critical ChangeLab are in line with the overall goals of the project and will actively support their successful delivery. The following five key communication objectives have been defined to achieve this.

- **demonstrates the impact** of the research resulted from the examination of current education institutions and the investigation into youth perspectives on democracy, highlighting the **robust evidence at the basis** of it
- **engage participants** in the **implementation** of the Critical ChangeLabs model and **facilitate a dialogue** with the community of educators, researchers and other relevant stakeholders to involve them in the **co-creation** and **co-design** of the model
- **demonstrates the impact** of the Critical ChangeLab Model of Democratic Pedagogy and **multiply knowledge** among education professionals, by sharing insights into the development process (design, co-creation, implementation and evaluation)
- **advocate change** following the evaluation of the process, impact, and socio-economic cost of the CCLab model and its development process (focus groups, different iterations etc.)

Table 4: Outline of Communication Objectives

CO1 ACTIVATE ENGAGEMENT

CO2 FACILITATE DIALOGUE

CO3 DEMONSTRATE IMPACT

CO4 ADVOCATE CHANGE

CO5 MULTIPLY KNOWLEDGE

The Communication Plan will further describe how these objectives will be achieved by reaching the right audiences at the right times through using the appropriate methods. The plan will identify how these objectives will aid in the growth, appraisal, adoption, and utilization of the outcomes of the Critical ChangeLab.

2.3.1 Activate Engagement

To achieve the Communication Objective 1 (Activate Engagement) we will engage different target audiences - in particular educational institutions and professionals, as well as youth - in some of the Critical ChangeLab activities. In such cases, the direct participation and active involvement of target audiences is essential to the successful completion of corresponding tasks and deliverables. Tasks that will require activating the engagement of target groups include (but are not limited to) Democracy Health Index (T1.1) where educational professionals at institutions are requested to assess their own democratic values and practices, the three PAR cycles of the Critical ChangeLabs (T1.4, T2.2, T2.3) where engagement is necessary for the implementation of the Critical ChangeLabs, the community empowerment activities, teacher training (T4.3) and youth mentoring (T4.4), require the active engagement of education professionals and young people respectively.

2.3.2 Facilitate Dialogue

Through Communication Objective 2 (Facilitate Dialogue) we want to ensure that the project remains participatory and open to input. We support the opening of the working process, objectives, and methodologies of the project to stakeholders and collaborators to provide their feedback, views and voices and contribute to the development of the Critical ChangeLab's outputs.

The tasks that require the communication strategy to support a dialogue include (but are not limited to) Task 3.1. Process evaluation, Task 3.2. Impact evaluation, Task 3.3 Socio-economic evaluation. AE will ensure that the visual identity and the messages are used in a consistent manner in the communication with external stakeholders.

2.3.3 Demonstrate Impact

Communication Objective 3 (Demonstrate Impact) will be predominantly achieved through dissemination measures, and it is closely aligned to the project objective that seeks to demonstrate a Robust Evidence Base. Its role is to emphasise the robust evidence and quality of research of the Critical ChangeLab outputs and will further support the achievement of the remaining two Communication Objectives - Advocate Change and Multiply Knowledge.

The deliverables at the basis of our narratives about the impact of the project research include (but are not limited to) D1.1 – Instrument: Democracy Health Questionnaire and Index, D1.2 – Everyday democracy in formal and non-formal education institutions, D1.3 – Youth perspectives on everyday democracy, D1.4 – Critical ChangeLab Model: Framework and Toolkit, as well as D3.1 – Critical ChangeLab process and recommendations

for practice, D3.2 – Critical ChangeLab Model for Democratic Pedagogy: Developing 21st Century Skills for Democratic Participation, and D3.3 – Critical ChangeLab impact evaluation.

2.3.4 Advocate Change

Communication Objective 4 (Advocate Change) will be achieved predominantly through dissemination and exploitation measures, targeting policy and decision-makers, technology providers, civil society organisations and educational professionals. By providing convincing arguments of how policy recommendations informed by research and innovation in Critical ChangeLab can be exploited, we can advocate change at the policy and decision-making level, in particular, advocate for the integration of our model into school curricula across EU states. Policy recommendations will also relate to technological development, which has an increasing impact on education and since the relation between young people and technology is a crucial theme of the project. Technology professionals will be engaged in roundtables precisely to ensure these learnings are taken up by tech companies.

In addition, we will also address formal and non-formal education professionals with D2.3 – Critical ChangeLab Educators' Handbook, to increase the chances of a successful adoption of the model in formal and non-formal education institutions and in the ways that the school curricula are delivered and in the evolution of curricula.

The deliverables at the basis of our narratives that advocate change are D4.2 – Policy Brief 1, D4.5 – Policy brief 2, D4.6 – Policy recommendations on citizenship education for sustainable European democracy, D3.4 Policy recommendations based on the socio-economic evaluation of the Critical ChangeLab Model.

2.3.5 Multiply Knowledge

Communication Objective 5 (Multiply Knowledge) is focused on communicating the “usable” resources made available within Critical ChangeLab and advocating for their uptake. This communication objective predominantly targets education professionals and institutions and will be achieved through communication, dissemination and exploitation measures, seeking to amplify the overall impact of the project by ensuring certain deliverables are clearly and convincingly presented to external stakeholders, to increase their adoption and expand our community of practice.

The deliverables that contribute to this objective include (but are not limited to) D2.3 – Critical ChangeLab Educators' Handbook, D3.1 – Critical ChangeLab process and recommendations for practice, D3.2 – Critical ChangeLab Model for Democratic Pedagogy: Developing 21st Century Skills for Democratic Participation, D4.3 – Critical ChangeLab Model of Democratic Pedagogy MOOC.

2.4 Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Targets

2.4.1 Communication Targets

Table 5: Overview of Communication KPIs

Comm. KPI No.	Project KPI No.	No. of actions	Type of action	Comm. Objectives	Target Group	Indicator	Measurement
CK1.1	K6.5	320	Digital Comm. Actions Social media posts	All	All	150,000	Total combined audience impressions from social media posts and paid ads on project partners' channels and the project's own LinkedIn channel
CK1.1	K6.5	320	Digital Comm. Actions Social media posts	All	All	1500	Total combined audience engagement from social media posts and paid ads on project partners' channels and the project's own LinkedIn channel
CK1.2	K6.5	1	Digital Comm Actions Project Website	All	All	3,000	Total website pageviews
CK1.3	K6.5	40	Digital Comm Actions Blog posts	All	All	4,000	*Total combined pageviews for the 30 blog posts and the Library section
CK1.4	K6.5	12	Digital Comm Actions Email Newsletters	All	All	40,000	Email newsletter reach

CK1.5	K6.5	40	Digital Comm Actions Voices of Youth Videos	Facilitate Dialogue	All	2,000	Video views
CK2	K6.3	2	Project Organised Conferences	Demonstrate Impact, Multiply Knowledge	All	10,000	Attendees
CK3	K6.5	2	Consortium Wide Press Releases	Activate Engagement, Demonstrate Impact	All	1,100	Members of press contacted

2.4.2 Dissemination Targets

Table 6: Overview of Exploitation KPIs

Diss. KPI No.	Project KPI No.	No. of actions	Type of action	Comm. Objectives	Target Group	Indicator	Measurement		
DK1	K7.1	16	Academic Publication	Demonstrate Impact	TG1	1,000	Researchers reached		
DK2	K5.3	57	Training in Critical ChangeLab Model		TG2	1,100	Educators trained through Critical ChangeLabs, teacher education and professional development actions.		
DK3	K7.1	30	Research events	Demonstrate Impact	TG1	500	Researchers reached		
DK4	K6.2	-	Publication of Critical ChangeLab Model Resources	Multiply Knowledge	TG2, TG4, TG5	8,500	Total number of individuals informed of the Critical ChangeLab Model resources across range of activities and channels.		
DK4.1	K6.2				TG2			7,000	Education professionals and young people in education informed of Model Resources
DK4.2	K6.1				TG4			1,000	Representatives of CSOs and industry informed of Model Resources
DK4.3	K6.1				TG5			500	Policy and decision-makers informed of Model Resources

DK5	K6.4	4	Publication of Critical ChangeLab Policy Briefs and Policy Recommendations	Advocate Change	TG1, TG2, TG4, TG5	6,000	Total number of individuals informed of the Critical ChangeLab Policy Publications across range of activities and channels.
DK5.1	K6.4				TG1	2,000	Researchers informed of the Policy Publications
DK5.2	K6.4				TG2	3,000	educational professionals and young people in education informed of Policy Publications
DK5.3	K6.4				TG4	500	CSO and Industry representatives Policy Publications
DK5.4	K6.4				TG5	500	Policy and decision-makers informed of Policy Publications

2.4.3 Exploitation Targets

Table 7: Overview of Exploitation KPIs

Expl. KPI No.	Project KPI No.	No. of actions	Type of action	Comm. Objectives	Target Group	Indicator	Measurement
EK1	K2.3, K3.2, K5.4, K4.7	98	Young people engaging with Critical ChangeLab	Facilitate Dialogue	TG3	1,500	Total young people actively engaged with Critical ChangeLab
EK1.1	K2.3	19	Critical ChangeLab (PAR Cycle 1)	Activate Engagement	TG3	200	Learners participating in Critical ChangeLab
EK1.2	K3.2	19	Critical ChangeLab (PAR Cycle 2)		TG3	400	Learners participating in Critical ChangeLab
EK1.3	K3.2	19	Critical ChangeLab (PAR Cycle 3)		TG3	400	Learners participating in Critical ChangeLab
EK1.4	K5.4	40	Critical ChangeLab Youth Mentorship		TG3	40	Young people mentored

EK1.5	K4.7	3	Youth Assembly Meetings		TG3	10	Young people involved in Youth assembly
EK2	K6.1, K3.3	80	Critical Change Labs	Multiply Knowledge	TG2, TG4	330	Total Critical ChangeLab Collaborators
EK2.1	K3.3				TG2	300	Educators actively engaged
EK2.2	K2.5				TG4	20	CSO and industry actively engaged
EK2.3	K6.1				TG2	10	Education departments actively engaged
EK3	K6.4	8	Online Workshops	Advocate Change	TG1, TG2, TG4, TG5	50	Workshop participants
EK4	K.2	1	MOOC	Facilitate Dialogue	TG3	200	MOOC Students

3.Channels

3.1 Defining Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Channels

The Communication Objectives will be achieved through a series of **Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation** measures undertaken within the project across a range of channels. While the exploitation of the project results is not confined to WP4, but takes place across all work packages, the Dissemination & Communication activities are intrinsically linked to the successful exploitation of the project results.

Communication activities are associated to Tasks 4.1 and 4.2 of WP4 and are led by AE of WP4 while Dissemination and Exploitation Activities take place within Tasks 4.3 and 4.4 of WP4 and are led by ALTEREURO, which is also responsible for leading WP4.

The audience focus will vary across Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation and different channels will be utilised to target the most appropriate audience groups.

Communication actions will take place across channels that have a broader audience and will include: research institutions, formal and non-formal education, young people and their families, CSOs and industry, as well as policy and decision makers. In the first part of the project, the communication activities were essential for creating awareness about and building the credibility of the project research and activities within the research community, as well as for actively engaging external participants, for example in the CCLabs.

Dissemination activities will occur through targeted channels to deliver the outcomes to those who can utilise and build upon the pedagogic and research outputs of Critical ChangeLab: educators, pedagogical coordinators, education institutions managers, CSOs and industry, policy and decision-makers. Dissemination measures will also support these target groups to engage and communicate with young people and their families. Dissemination activities started at the beginning of the project to build early buy-in and awareness with policy makers, civil society and business stakeholders, researchers and education professionals and will grow in the last two years of the project, as more and more outputs are published, and their targeted dissemination becomes imperative.

Exploitation measures take place across channels that are specifically created through the activities undertaken within teaching, learning and research conducted within the Critical ChangeLab project. The publication of Policy Briefs and Policy Recommendations is another exploitation measure that will ensure the extended use of the project outcomes in the form of policy recommendations to local, national or European government agents. The exploitation strategy becomes essential towards the end of the project, when all the outcomes can be presented as a complete methodology and framework built upon robust evidence to advocate change with decision-makers and education practitioners to ensure take-up of the methods beyond the lifetime of the project and ultimately policy change over a longer term.

The Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation measures will be undertaken to support the achievement of the five Communication Objectives. The successful implementation of each of these measures depends on answering the same three central questions.

1. **Audience:** Who are we trying to reach?
2. **Message:** What dialogue should we be having with our audience to achieve our objectives?

3. **Channel:** How and when will this message be delivered?

The selection of channels across Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation is informed by these three questions. All channels utilised within the project will be respective of the audience and, if a channel involves the collection of audience data, it will be GDPR compliant.

3.2 Communication Channels

3.2.1 *Visual Identity*

The purpose of the visual identity for Critical ChangeLab is to create a consistent and recognizable representation of the project. It helps to establish a cohesive and professional image and facilitates effective communication and branding. The visual identity includes elements such as logos, colour schemes, typography, and graphic elements, which are applied to various communication channels, including the project's website, social media platforms, and promotional materials. By having a well-defined visual identity, Critical ChangeLab can consistently convey its message across all partner channels in a visually consistent manner.

The project branding and visual identity guidelines (Annex 2) were developed by the designer Stefan Eibelwimmer who was selected by AE. The designer responded to a Creative Brief prepared by AE informed by the perspectives of consortium partners collected during Visual Identity Workshop led by AE at the Project-Kick Off Meeting in MI. The designer presented the project consortium with five different proposals for the visual identity of the Critical ChangeLab and consortium members voted on each of these proposals until a final proposal was selected by a majority of consortium partners.

Visual Identity as a Decentralised Identity

The Creative Brief outlined how a *Decentralised Identity* would be necessary as the visual identity will be used by multiple partner organisations and would need to be both flexible and adaptable while retaining a broader trans-organisational coherence. The development of an adaptive and open identity was requested so that the project's identity could be successfully and easily incorporated into each of the project partner's individual communication strategies and approaches.

Visual Identity Templates

The designer provided a package of templates and guidelines in the Visual Identity that can be utilised by partners for a range of communication and dissemination activities.

These include:

- Project Logo
- Project Logo variations for the sections of the project
- Graphic Elements to distinguish the different parts of the project
- Website banners and graphical layout
- Letterhead template, press release template, report template
- Powerpoint presentation template
- Social Media template overlays
- Colour palette
- Typography

3.2.2 Project Website

The project website will be hosted by Ars Electronica and will be the central location for management, distribution and dissemination of information, news, Policy Briefs and educational resources of the Critical ChangeLab project, as well as events and other relevant information for Critical ChangeLabs.

Critical ChangeLab news, updates and announcements will be posted on the website following the publication of project outputs across all work packages. Producing the contents of the blog articles and announcements on the website will be led by AE in collaboration with Critical ChangeLab partners responsible for specific project outcomes that are to be communicated.

Alongside blog articles about the progress of the project, we set up a Library page that serves as a repository for all the research and publications (deliverables) resulted from the project. In time, the Library page will be restructured, i.e. the outputs and publications will be categorized by target audiences (e.g. policy-makers, researchers and educational professionals) to make it easier for visitors to access and sort through content.

Moreover, some of the resources produced will be published in different languages on the website, more specifically those used for activities that have been conducted in local languages and for which materials have already been translated.

3.2.3 Social media

The Critical ChangeLab will primarily utilise the existing social media channels of the consortium partners, that already have an established audience with a combined reach of more than 350,000. Moreover, a LinkedIn account for the project has been set-up by the coordinator (OULU) and is managed by AE. All major outputs of the project, news of dissemination activities and videos will be published on this account and reshared by partners. The decision to create a LinkedIn account for the project (and not subsequent social media channels, such as Facebook/Instagram/X) is motivated by an assessment of the target audiences of our project (in particular researchers & academics, educators, CSOs, policy makers) and the knowledge of where/how they can best be reached with the type of resources the project makes available. The structure of the library section will, at times, inform the social media and paid ads campaigns, which will also be structured according to target group.

To ensure the communication actions appear cohesive across the different social media channels of the partner organisations, social media templates are incorporated within the Visual Guidelines of the Critical ChangeLab. Moreover, AE shares visuals and posts content with all the partners, whenever important announcement at the project level are made. AE has set up a social media calendar for this purpose. A unique hashtag #CriticalChangeLab will also be used across all social media platforms and channels to ensure the project is consistently searchable and taggable.

The social media platforms that will be utilised are X, LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram.

3.2.4 Newsletter

The email newsletter leverages the consortium's subscribers' lists to regularly inform the professional target groups of the project on usable results, learnings, and participatory opportunities. In addition to this, a project newsletter has been set up and is being used to send regular updates to subscribers. This strategy was adopted to ensure a more accurate

targeting of relevant audiences. The newsletter strategy aims to reach over 40,000 impressions in total.

The newsletters will communicate and disseminate regular updates about the project's working process, criteria, methodologies, as well as sharing of usable results, learnings, and participatory opportunities with the professional target groups.

3.2.5 Video

Video will be used predominantly as a channel for the Youth Voices video campaign, where 40 young people will produce vlogs and video statements on their views on a sustainable future and reflect the project's tools. Informed consent would be asked from young people and their guardians before producing these videos. The videos will be published on social media and shared across partners channels, and may be shared and promoted by young people themselves on their own channels. The videos are intended to empower and give youth a voice, create peer to peer inspiration and interest in active citizenship amongst young people, and help educators better identify issues and vocabularies to address youth.

3.2.6 Press releases

Press releases will serve as an important communication channel in the Critical ChangeLab project, contributing to the project's visibility, outreach, and engagement with various target groups, including the media and the general public.

Two press releases will be issued half-way through, around the publication of D 4.3 (MOOC) and PAR Cycle 3, and at the end of the project once all the research outputs and publications have been made available online.

3.3 Dissemination Channels

3.3.1 Critical ChangeLabs

Critical ChangeLabs themselves function as a unique and integral dissemination channel for the Critical ChangeLab project, including its process and usable results and learnings. These labs serve as platforms for open dialogue, collaboration, and the exchange of ideas

among participants, enabling the dissemination of the project's working process, criteria, and methodologies to civil society.

During the Critical ChangeLabs, the project opens up its working process, criteria, and methodologies to all participants including learners. This means that participants can actively engage with the project, understand its inner workings, and contribute to its development. Through this participatory approach, the project ensures transparency and fosters a sense of ownership, and a community of individuals (the participants) invested in the project's objectives and outcomes that become project ambassadors when sharing their experience.

3.3.2 Teacher education and professional development actions

Teacher education and professional development actions in the Critical ChangeLab project serve as an important dissemination channel for promoting the project's goals and outcomes, particularly in the context of cultivating democracy in daily practices and embracing participatory approaches to democracy education.

These actions include:

- courses designed for teacher education students – aiming to inform future educators about the Critical ChangeLab principles, leveraging on the connection of several of the academic partners to teacher training colleges (In Finland, Ireland, Spain)
- seminars, and panels targeting professional educators – aiming to engage educators in discussions about democratic practices in education, share knowledge, and exchange ideas
- a Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) on the Critical ChangeLab Model of Democratic Pedagogy that is open to all citizens

Moreover, the MOOC on the Critical ChangeLab Model of Democratic Pedagogy aims to reach a broader audience, allowing citizens from diverse backgrounds to access and learn about the project's principles and democratic pedagogy. By offering this course, the project promotes its ideas and methodologies beyond the immediate project stakeholders and extends its impact to a wider audience.

By utilizing teacher education and professional development actions as dissemination channels, the project maximizes its reach and influence within the education community, and increases the chances of the model's integration into the educational curricula. These activities facilitate the exchange of knowledge, foster awareness and understanding of democratic practices in education, and contribute to the overall goals of the project.

3.3.3 Direct outreach

Direct outreach with researchers, CSOs, industry, and policy-makers will serve as a crucial channel for disseminating the outputs of the Critical ChangeLab project. By actively engaging with these key stakeholders, the project aims to reach a wider audience and maximize the impact of its research and innovation outputs. Through direct outreach, the Critical ChangeLab project can effectively communicate and disseminate the project's working process, criteria, methodologies, and results. This allows **researchers** to stay **informed** about the project's progress and findings, fostering collaborations and knowledge exchange. Engaging **CSOs** is vital as it opens up the project to a broader range of perspectives and expertise. By **actively involving** these organizations, the project ensures that the research and practice outputs are relevant and applicable to societal challenges. CSOs are actively involved in realising the PAR cycles, are approached through mailing lists of the partner organisations and in particular EuroAlter.

Direct outreach with industry partners (in particular, professional educators) is crucial for the practical implementation of the **Critical ChangeLab Model** in diverse settings. By collaborating and disseminating the tools and methods to industry stakeholders, the project seeks to facilitate the adoption of the model and its outputs in real-world contexts, in particular in the delivery and adaptation of school curricula across EU states.

Furthermore, establishing direct contact with **policy-makers** creates opportunities for the project **to influence decision-making** processes. All partners in the project will be involved in identifying and communicating with policy-makers from their countries, to ensure local and national pertinence and buy-in of the policy maker. Contact with policy makers will be 'snow balled' through the project by engaging policy makers in identifying more colleagues that could be interested. The opportunity of the election of the new European Parliament members and the new members workprogram of the Commission will be used as an

opportunity to establish connections and shape institutional work over the coming mandate. By effectively disseminating the outputs to policy and decision-makers, the project can contribute to evidence-based policy-making and increase the potential for the project's outcomes to be integrated into relevant policy frameworks, including school programs at local, regional and national levels.

3.3.4 Conference presentations, seminars, expert panels and civil society moments

Each academic partner will lead production of 4 papers to be presented at conferences, and ALTEREURO will ensure the coordination of this process, and AE derive wider communications material from this occasions. Broader academic audiences will be reached at conferences such as ECER by the European Education Research Association, AERA (American Educational Research Association), International Conference on Computer-Supported Collaborative Learning, International Conference of the Learning Sciences, Annual Conference on Youth Studies, Children and Youth Conference, Journal of Youth Studies Conference, Participatory Design Conference, Fablearn Conference Europe, Interaction Design and Children, Interact, ACM Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems, International Conference on Communities & Technologies. Academic presentations and use of CCLAB methodologies will also be proposed to events with a wider public that mixes researchers, civil society practitioners and young people such as civil society festivals, democracy festivals, open days and similar events.

3.3.5 Project-led conferences

Two conferences led by the Critical ChangeLab are planned to take place within the project. These conferences will take place at events such as Ars Electronica Festival and the NECE network conference (Networking European Citizenship Education) reaching more than 10,000 people from the general public and professionals.

3.3.6 Workshops and focus groups

Workshops and focus groups will serve as an important dissemination channel within the Critical ChangeLab project, particularly for engaging policy-makers, CSOs and industry stakeholders. These interactive and collaborative sessions provide an opportunity to directly

involve these key stakeholders in the project, ensuring their active participation and contribution to the dissemination process.

By organizing workshops and focus groups with policy-makers, the Critical ChangeLab project can share its research and practice outputs directly with those responsible for shaping policies and making decisions. These sessions provide a platform for exchanging ideas, discussing recommendations, and exploring potential policy implications of the project's findings. Through meaningful engagement with policy-makers, the project can influence policy development and contribute to evidence-based decision-making processes.

Workshops and focus groups offer a space for CSOs to actively participate in the dissemination of the project outputs. These sessions allow for a collaborative exchange of knowledge, experiences, and perspectives between the project team and civil society representatives. By involving CSOs, the project ensures that the research and practice outputs are aligned with the needs and priorities of the communities they represent. Moreover, it enables the project to establish partnerships and networks that can support the implementation of the Critical ChangeLab Model in diverse settings.

Professional educators are a target group to be involved in workshops and focus groups both to introduce the Critical ChangeLab model - as it might apply to various challenges they face in delivering school curricula or in making schools in general more democratic spaces -, and also to generate initiatives for further development of the Critical ChangeLab model after the project has formally finished. These professional educators will be identified through a) schools that have been involved in the PAR cycle testing of CCL, b) newsletters and similar of teacher associations, c) training colleges of teachers.

Workshops and focus groups provide an opportunity to engage industry stakeholders in the dissemination process. By inviting representatives from relevant industries, the project can explore potential applications of the Critical ChangeLab Model and its outputs within different sectors. These sessions facilitate knowledge transfer, foster innovation, and promote the practical implementation of the project's findings in industry settings. Additionally, collaborating with industry stakeholders ensures the project's outputs are applicable and relevant to real-world contexts.

It is worth noting that workshops and focus groups are not only conducted with policy-makers, CSOs, and industry stakeholders individually but also encourage their participation in joint sessions. This creates opportunities for interdisciplinary discussions, knowledge sharing, and collaboration among these different stakeholder groups. The interactive nature of these sessions allows for richer insights, diverse perspectives, and greater potential for co-creation and mutual learning.

3.3.7 Academic journals, book publications and conference papers

A comprehensive publication of results will target international, peer-reviewed, high impact journals such as Journal of Learning Sciences, Journal of New Approaches in Educational Research, Journal of Youth Studies, Journal of Youth and Adolescence, Youth and Society, Democracy & Education Journal, International Journal of Educational Research Review, Media, Culture & Society, Young, CoDesign, Digital Creativity, British Journal of Educational Technology, Learning, Media and Technology. Dissemination through youth-focused forums such as The Global Forum of Modern Direct Democracy, World Bank Group Youth Summit, European Youth Foundation and Youth2Youth will be also considered to reach professionals, as well as policy and decision-makers in the field of youth work. Each academic partner is responsible for submitting at least 4 papers to academic conferences and to high impact journals (resulting in at least 16 high impact paper publications), and the cross-country comparative and innovative nature of the project will be used to seek a book contract with a leading academic publisher. At least 10 paper presentations at conferences are anticipated to have taken place by the mid-point of the project to ensure wide academic awareness of the project at an early stage and drive registration on newsletters, social media and similar of academics and researchers.

3.3.8 Publication of Open Data

Dissemination of results will also be accomplished through early and open data sharing following open science practices, as described in detail in 1.2.5. Considering the interdisciplinarity and number of international partners in the project, particular attention will be paid to build a robust Data Management Plan (D5.2 DMP) that ensures that the generated data are made available during and beyond the lifetime of the project following FAIR principles. Open repositories such as Zenodo will be utilised alongside other European

Commission (EC) channels and services such as CORDIS to support dissemination and exploitation of the project outputs.

3.4 Exploitation Channels

3.4.1 *Critical ChangeLabs*

The participation of educators alongside CSOs and industry partners in each of the Critical ChangeLabs themselves will be fundamental to contributing to the exploitation of the projects results. Participants will have a hands-on opportunity to directly experience the methods of the Critical ChangeLab Model. The Critical ChangeLabs will be the most significant measure to facilitate the exploitation of the project's research, practice outputs, innovations in democratic pedagogy and approaches to engaging young people with everyday democracy.

3.4.2 *Youth Mentorship Program*

The Critical ChangeLab youth and mentorship program will play a crucial role as an exploitation channel for the Critical ChangeLab project. This program aims to foster active and inclusive citizenship among young people, supporting them to take initiative and engage in democratic processes, whether through everyday democracy or activist actions. Through this program, the project expects to achieve its objective of increasing youth active citizenship and promoting diversity and inclusion as key values in democratic societies.

The youth and mentorship program operates within the framework of the Critical ChangeLabs, providing direct experiences with the Critical ChangeLab Model of Democratic Pedagogy and supporting resources. The program specifically focuses on mentoring 40 young learners, with a special emphasis on individuals from groups historically underrepresented in democratic processes. This targeted approach aims to foster youth activist skills and enhance youth participation in representative structures. By providing mentorship and guidance, the project supports these young learners in cultivating their leadership abilities, empowering them to become active agents of change within their communities.

3.4.3 Youth Assembly

The Youth Assembly is an external governing body convened for the project and is described within D5.1. It consists of ten young people from different European countries who will be actively participate in the project will be another channel that supports the exploitation of the Critical ChangeLab.

The direct involvement of young leaders will ensure that the voices and perspectives of youth are not only included in the project's activities, decision-making processes, and discussions, but will ensure that the knowledge generated from the project feedback directly into their respective communities of young people.

3.4.4 Critical ChangeLab Resource Library

The Critical ChangeLab Resource library hosted on the project website will host resources that can be directly utilised by educators. These resources include the Critical ChangeLab Framework and Toolkit, and the ChangeLab Educators' Handbook, which will provide educators working in formal and non-formal learning environment with open education resources with clear instructions that can be immediately adopted and integrated into existing educational programs. The Critical ChangeLab Resource Library will therefore become a central channel contributing to the exploitation of the project in a range of learning environments beyond Critical ChangeLabs implemented within the project.

3.4.5 Critical ChangeLab MOOC

The MOOC for training educators and the policy recommendations on citizenship education for developing 21st century skills for democratic participation will ensure the sustainability of the project and contribute to increasing its impact. The MOOC will be an exploitation channel that specifically targets educators and students participating in teacher education and professional development but will also be open to all citizens, and as such will contribute to generate awareness about the importance of cultivating democracy in daily practices and embrace participatory approaches to democracy education.

3.4.6 Policy Publications

Policy publications will be made available in the Critical Change Resource Library and will be and consist of the four following deliverables:

No.	Deliverable	WP	Est. Delivery	Partner
D4.2	Policy Brief 1	WP4	M12	ISRZ
D4.5	Policy Brief 2	WP4	M30	UB
D4.6	Policy recommendations on citizenship education for sustainable European democracy	WP4	M30	ALTEREURO
D3.4	Policy recommendations based on the socio-economic evaluation of the Critical ChangeLab Model	WP3	M35	UB

Policy Briefs are fundamental tools for the exploitation of a project’s results. By providing a comprehensive and organized summary of the practice and research findings of the Critical ChangeLab project, they help policy- and decision-makers understand and utilize the outcomes of the project. Policy Briefs will highlight the relevance and implications of the Critical ChangeLab for informing policy and practice at various levels, including at an organisational, local, national and transnational level. The Policy Briefs will be published within the Critical ChangeLab resource library and communicated directly to policy-makers through active outreach by consortium partners, and with the support of the communication and dissemination channels utilised by the project. The Policy Briefs developed within the framework of Critical ChangeLab will emphasise how the project results can be applied in real-world settings, Policy Briefs help bridge the gap between research and policy implementation.

4. Target Groups

The Communication Objectives of the Critical ChangeLab will be realized through the strategic engagement of five key audience groups: researchers and research institutions, educators in formal and non-formal settings, young people and their families as part of the general public, CSOs alongside industries, and policy and decision-makers. By successfully

engaging with these groups, we can influence educational policies, assure curriculum implementation and improve youth–civic interaction. Every engagement is expected to take into account the unique interests, needs, communication channels, challenges, and behaviours of the specific group. The ultimate objective is to rejuvenate democracy in Europe by shaping an informed, involved, and resilient generation of young people, capable of constructive dialogue and change.

Table 8: Outline of the 5 Audience Target Groups of Critical ChangeLab

TG1 RESEARCHERS AND RESEARCH INSTITUTIONS

TG2 FORMAL & NON-FORMAL EDUCATION PROFESSIONALS

TG3 YOUNG PEOPLE, THEIR FAMILIES & THE GENERAL PUBLIC

TG4 CIVIL SOCIETY ORGANISATIONS AND INDUSTRY

TG5 POLICY AND DECISION MAKERS

4.1 Target Group 1: Researchers and research institutions

The audience of Target Group 1 (TG1) predominantly comprises individuals and institutions committed to studying and better understanding the intersection of youth involvement and democracy education. They are focused on exploring the mechanisms, impacts, and possibilities within this specialized field.

4.1.1 Audience profile of TG1

Table 9: Audience profile of Target Group 1 (TG1)

INTERESTS	This audience is primarily interested in understanding and influencing the ways in which young people engage with democratic values and processes. Their studies often delve into matters of policy, curriculum development, citizenship education, and societal trends in Europe and beyond.
NEEDS AND PREFERENCES	They need access to up-to-date research, participation data, policy developments, and a direct line to the youth demographic and educational institutions. They value collaborative networks and interactive platforms that allow for a wide range of perspectives and insights.
COMMUNICATION CHANNELS	Their communication mostly happens through academic journals specializing in democracy education, research papers, educational forums, conferences, and email networks. They also leverage digital social platforms, online webinars, and workshops for wider discussions and collaborations.
CHALLENGES	They often face challenges in obtaining consistent, comprehensive data regarding youth engagement, securing research funding, and finding ways to directly engage and impact youth and educational policy in a practical sense.
BEHAVIOUR	Researchers in the field of youth and democracy education possess a strong combination of academic rigor and hands-on engagement. They approach their work with empathy, openness, deep curiosity and are fundamentally motivated to improve the democratic processes for young people.
INFLUENCE	Given their area of specialization, these researchers significantly influence decision-making in education policies, youth outreach programmes, and contribute to the ongoing dialogue on democratic pedagogy within Europe and beyond.

4.1.2 Relationship of TG1 to Critical ChangeLab

Connected communication objectives

CO2	FACILITATE DIALOGUE
CO3	DEMONSTRATE IMPACT

The engagement of youth and democracy education researchers as Critical ChangeLab partners is of paramount importance to the project success and to ensure the project outputs have impact beyond the scope of the project.

Further education researchers will be reached through publications, attendance at conferences and leveraging of existing networks.

Additionally, the project will actively seek to establish links and engage in dialogue with researchers involved in other Horizon Europe projects focused on democracy and education to work towards multiplying the outputs across projects by activating and benefiting from an expanded network of partners.

4.1.3 Key messages for reaching TGI

The key messages for researchers and research institutions should highlight the project's collaborative nature, the innovative research being undertaken, the opportunities for networking and collaboration, and the accessibility of the project's findings for researchers interested in youth and democracy education.

- **New Knowledge:** Showcase the innovative research being conducted within the Critical ChangeLab project. Emphasize how the project outcomes provide valuable practical insight into methodologies for supporting active democratic citizenship among young people, and draws observations about the changing needs in democratic citizenship education based on a cross-country comparative approach.
- **Open Data:** Highlight the availability of open data sets created through the research and evaluation undertaken within actions of the Critical ChangeLab project. Promote how these open data sets could be utilised for follow-up research or to investigate alternative research questions that are not addressed within the scope of the Critical ChangeLab project.
- **Networking Opportunities:** Emphasise the diverse range of expertise within the Critical ChangeLab consortium. Promote the opportunities for networking and knowledge exchange available through the conferences organised by the consortium partners, where researchers can learn from one another and establish connections.

4.1.4 Channels used for reaching TGI

COMMUNICATION

DISSEMINATION

EXPLOITATION

Website	Conference presentations,	Critical ChangeLab
Social media (in particular LinkedIn & Paid Ads)	seminars, expert panels, civil society events	Resource Library
Newsletter	Project-led conferences Academic journals and conference papers Publication of Open Data Direct Outreach	

4.2 Target Group 2: Formal and non-formal education professionals

This audience includes teachers, facilitators, guides, pedagogical coordinators as well as directors and managers operating in both formal (such as lower and upper secondary schools, vocational schools, colleges, and universities) and non-formal (such as youth centres, art and technology centres, makerspaces, sports clubs, scouts and other entities organising activities for youth during their free time) learning environments within Europe.

4.2.1 Audience profile of TG2

Table 10: Audience profile of Target Group 2 (TG2)

INTERESTS	These professionals are devoted to facilitating learning and improving educational outcomes. They are interested in pedagogical progress, student engagement, curriculum development, and innovation in education.
NEEDS AND PREFERENCES	This group requires access to comprehensive curriculum guides, teaching resources, professional development opportunities, and platforms for collaboration and exchange. They value student-centered approaches, inclusivity, diversity, and are open to newer ways of teaching that provide better learning experiences.
COMMUNICATION CHANNELS	Communication typically happens through educational conferences, workshops, seminars, professional networks, emails, educational magazines, and online forums dedicated to education professionals. Digital platforms for communication and collaboration are also widely used.

CHALLENGES	They are often tasked with managing large classrooms, dealing with diverse student needs, keeping up with changes in educational policies, adapting to changes in technology, and finding ways to engage students in various learning contexts.
BEHAVIOUR	Education professionals are generally patient, empathetic, and dedicated. They are typically open to learning and adopting new methods that improve teaching effectiveness and student learning outcomes.
INFLUENCE	These professionals can exert considerable influence over decisions related to curriculum implementation, teaching methodologies, and student evaluation. They have a crucial role in shaping the education system, and in turn, influencing future generations.

4.2.2 Relationship of TG2 to Critical ChangeLab & Objectives

Connected communication objectives

CO1	ACTIVATE ENGAGEMENT
CO2	FACILITATE DIALOGUE
CO4	ADVOCATE CHANGE
CO5	MULTIPLY KNOWLEDGE

Formal and non-formal education professionals are effectively the most important target group for Critical ChangeLab as the outputs developed will have the most utilitarian value for this group and can therefore deliver significant impact.

Education professionals will be actively engaged in the CCLabs, invited to give their feedback and participate in the co-creation of CCLab model. In facilitating a dialogue with the educators, we not only disseminate the model, but ensure that this target group can also become a voice for the project and help further disseminate and exploit its outputs.

Each of the Critical ChangeLabs will have education institutions as direct partners who will in turn act as multipliers within their networks. Educators involved in teacher training facilities will be also engaged in activities focused on disseminating and leveraging the

project's outcomes and outputs in a knowledge exchange. Finally, as direct users of the model, they will be able to support us in advocating for changes to the school curricula to include democratic pedagogy practices and models.

4.2.3 Key messages & channels for reaching TG2

The key messages for formal and non-formal education professionals should highlight the project's innovative pedagogical approaches, resources for curriculum enhancement, opportunities for professional development and collaboration, focus on student-centered education, inclusivity, and diversity, relevance to current policies, and the potential to make a lasting impact on future generations.

- **Innovative Pedagogical Approaches:** Highlight how the Critical ChangeLab Model support pedagogical innovation. Emphasize the value of incorporating these approaches into formal and non-formal learning environments.
- **Curriculum Enhancement:** Showcase Critical ChangeLab Model, and accompanying resources that can support and enrich existing curricula. Promote how the Critical ChangeLab MOOC can be utilised within diverse curriculum programs. Highlight the relevance of these resources in addressing diverse student needs and promoting inclusivity.
- **Professional Development Opportunities:** Communicate the availability of professional development opportunities offered within the project. Highlight how these opportunities can enhance educators' pedagogical skills, provide access to new teaching methodologies, foster collaboration among peers, and create further professional opportunities.
- **Collaboration and Exchange:** Emphasize the opportunities within the project activities and dissemination measures for collaboration and knowledge transfer, where educators can connect with their peers, share best practices, and exchange ideas. Highlight the value of this collaborative learning environment in promoting professional growth.

- **Youth-Centered Approaches:** Share stories on how young people engage with the CriticalChange Labs. Showcase through the perspective of young people how these approaches can foster student engagement, promote critical thinking, and improve overall educational experiences.
- **Inclusive and Diverse Education:** Demonstrate the project's emphasis on inclusivity and diversity in education. Communicate how the project promotes strategies and resources such as the Critical ChangeLab Code-of-Conduct that cater to diverse student populations, ensuring equal learning opportunities for all.
- **Relevance to Changing Educational Policies:** Position the project outputs as aligned with current educational policies across Europe and critically reflect changes in technology. Emphasize how the project offers practical solutions and resources that help educators adapt to these changes and meet evolving educational requirements.
- **Impact on Future Generations:** Emphasize the role of education professionals in shaping the education system and influencing the lives of future generations. Highlight the opportunity to contribute to positive change by incorporating the project's outputs into teaching practices.

4.2.4 Channels used for reaching TG2

COMMUNICATION	DISSEMINATION	EXPLOITATION
Website	Critical ChangeLab	Critical Changelabs
Social media (in particular LinkedIn & Paid Ads)	Teacher education and professional development	Critical ChangeLab Resource Library
Newsletter	actions Direct Outreach Policy and practitioner roundtables	Critical ChangeLab MOOC

4.3 Target Group 3: Young people, their families and the general public

This is the broadest target group and encompasses a wide range of individuals, including young people (from school-age children to young adults), their immediate family members, and the broader public. These audience members vary tremendously in their backgrounds, life experiences, and perspectives.

4.3.1 Audience profile of TG3

Table 11: Audience profile of Target Group 3 (TG3)

INTERESTS	Interests will differ significantly across this audience. Young people may be particularly interested in education, entertainment, technology, social events, and youth culture. Meanwhile, family members may care about health, safety, financial stability, and opportunities for their kids; the general public's interests would be vast and varied, including news, finance, society issues, trends, and more.
NEEDS AND PREFERENCES	Young people need to access education, societal and peer interactions, and opportunities for growth and fun. Families seek resources and information that can aid their children's development and enrichment. The general public needs access to reliable news, information and resources about numerous topics that affect daily life.
COMMUNICATION CHANNELS	Digital platforms, including social media, apps, emails, and websites, are common communication channels for young people. For families and the general public, other channels could also include print media, TV, radio, newsletters, community meetings, and more.
CHALLENGES	Young people often struggle with identity formation, academic pressures, and digital overexposure. Families may face challenges around maintaining work-life balance, health and wellness, and financial management. The general public faces challenges contingent on their personal circumstances and the socio-political climate.
BEHAVIOUR	This group exhibits a wide range of behaviours, largely dependent on their personal circumstances, socio-economic status, and individual personalities.
INFLUENCE	In democratic societies, this group can be powerful in influencing decision-making at family, community, and even national levels, as their collective voice and votes contribute to shaping the societal structure, norms, and policies.

4.3.2 Relationship of TG3 to Critical ChangeLab & Objectives

Connected communication objectives

CO1 **ACTIVATE ENGAGEMENT**

CO2 **FACILITATE DIALOGUE**

While education professionals can be the primary target of the project's communication and dissemination measures, young people are effectively the end-users of the **Critical ChangeLab Model**. Having a lasting impact on young people is completely crucial for Critical ChangeLab to achieve its goals, and thus getting them engaged in activities and dialogue is essential.

Communication actions targeting young people will predominantly take place through measures that support educators in their engagement with young people. In addition to these, there will also be a range of communication actions targeting young people directly, most notably through the Voices of Youth campaign and through establishing the Youth Assembly.

Furthermore, each organization that implements the **Critical ChangeLab Model** will directly engage with 150 young people during the project, reaching a total of 1500 individuals. The focus is on 11–18-year-olds, with the age range varying across each Critical ChangeLab and PAR cycle. The actions of the learners and the artifacts created at the Labs will also familiarize parents, siblings, and friends/peers with our model and approach.

Outputs and outcomes of the Critical ChangeLab will also be presented at events such as *create your world* program for young people and their families at the Ars Electronica Festival and the NECE (Networking European Citizenship Education) network conference, where more than 10,000 people from the general public are expected to be reached.

4.3.3 Key messages & channels for reaching target group

- **Activate the Agency of Young People:** Highlight the importance of empowering young people to be active participants in shaping their own

future and society. Let young people tell their own stories through actions such as the Youth Voices campaign and actively encouraging young people engaged in Critical ChangeLabs or the Youth Assembly to take initiative in voicing their own experiences, views and reflections on the project.

- **Transformation through Narration:** Emphasize how the **Critical ChangeLab Model** itself fosters a culture of transformation through storytelling, allowing young people to develop unique skills and perspectives that can empower them.
- **Collaboration and Co-creation:** Highlight how young people can co-create with educators, creatives, critical thinkers and organizations from across Europe to work towards shared goals.
- **Impactful Outputs:** Showcase the tangible outputs and outcomes of the Critical ChangeLab project produced by young people, such as innovative projects, prototypes, and ideas that have the potential to make a real difference in society.
- **Inclusivity and Diversity:** Emphasize the project's commitment to inclusivity and diversity, showcasing how Critical ChangeLab provides opportunities for young people from diverse and disadvantaged backgrounds to contribute their unique perspectives and experiences.
- **Everyday Democracy and Community Impact:** Demonstrate the positive impact that Critical ChangeLab has on the broader community, as young people engage with and inspire their peers, neighbours, and community members through their projects and ideas.
- **Inspiration and Personal Growth:** Showcase stories and examples of young people who have participated in the Critical ChangeLab project, highlighting how it has inspired their personal growth, expanded their horizons, and provided new opportunities.

4.3.4 Channels used for reaching TG3

COMMUNICATION	DISSEMINATION	EXPLOITATION
Website	Critical ChangeLabs	Critical ChangeLabs
Social Media		Youth Mentorship Program
Newsletter		Youth Assembly
Video		
Press releases		

4.4 Target Group 4: Civil society organisations and industry

This group comprises a wide range of entities, including non-profits, Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs), and private corporations. The types of organisations anticipated to be most responsive to the goals and activities of the Critical ChangeLab project include FabLabs, tech companies, incubators, activist organisations, libraries, environmental NGOs, and art institutions. These organisations are expected to be located within the European Union and in particular within each of the 19 countries where the Critical ChangeLabs will take place.

Civil Society Organisations (CSOs) and industry partners that make up this group will be diverse in size and focus, spanning everything from small community initiatives and possibly even large multi-national enterprises. It is anticipated that the organisations reached within this group will already be engaging in some ways with themes surrounding youth engagement, democracy and civic education.

4.4.1 Audience profile of TG4

Table 12: Audience profile of Target Group 4 (TG4)

INTERESTS	This group is deeply interested in social impact, corporate social responsibility, sustainability, diversity inclusion, innovative solutions and continuous skill growth and education. They are committed to promoting democratic values, contributing to societal growth, and fostering a culture of innovation.
NEEDS AND PREFERENCES	Their needs are expected to primarily revolve around civic engagement, sustainability, technology and society, and democracy education or workforce learning focused on social impact. They prefer to engage in

	collaboration, use best practices, and pursue innovative, practical solutions that align with their values and make a significant contribution to society.
COMMUNICATION CHANNELS	These organizations primarily make use of professional conferences, webinars, seminars, newsletters, and digital platforms like social media and online forums to communicate and gather information. They also rely on authoritative publications and reports within their specific sectors.
CHALLENGES	Their challenges often lie in keeping pace with youth engagement, evolving technologies, adapting to regulatory changes, managing resources, fostering civic mindsets and cultures of sustainability, and implementing best practices in line with diverse and evolving societal needs.
BEHAVIOUR	Organisations reached within this group are expected to be proactive and adaptive entities that anticipate social change, engage in critical digital transformations, and seek innovative strategies to enhance their practices. They also exhibit a strong commitment to community engagement, social responsibility, and industry transformation.
INFLUENCE	Their decision-making processes are influenced by various factors, including data-driven insights, benefits to stakeholders, compliance requirements, and alignment with organizational values. Key leaders within these organizations, industry trends, and regulatory bodies also play a significant role in shaping their decisions.

4.4.2 Relationship of TG4 to Critical ChangeLab & Objectives

Connected communication objectives

CO2	FACILITATE DIALOGUE
CO3	DEMONSTRATE IMPACT
CO5	MULTIPLY KNOWLEDGE

Through the Critical ChangeLabs, many of the organisations reached within this target group will actively collaborate with the project through partnerships with the individual Critical ChangeLabs, while others will be engaged through the project’s broader communication activities and events.

4.4.3 Key messages & channels for reaching TG4

CSOs and industry are expected to respond to key messages that showcase how Critical Changelab and its outputs can be utilized to increase civic engagement, make a meaningful social impact, foster innovation, develop skills, promote democracy education, and provide opportunities for professional growth and networking within a responsible and sustainable framework.

- **Social Impact and Sustainability:** Highlight how the Critical ChangeLab project and the resources and outputs created within the project can be utilised by CSOs and industry partners to increase civic engagement and make a meaningful social impact and contribute to sustainable development goals.
- **Collaboration for Innovation:** Emphasize the value of collaboration between organizations and the Critical ChangeLab project and its partner organisations, showcasing how it fosters innovative solutions and promotes the development of practical strategies that align with societal needs.
- **Generational Responsibility:** Showcase how the Critical ChangeLab project aligns with the values of corporate social responsibility and more specifically how the Critical ChangeLab can provide organizations with a platform to actively engage young people in initiatives that address critical social issues and promote positive change.
- **Skill Development:** Highlight how collaborating with the Critical ChangeLab project and learning from the **Critical ChangeLab Model** can offer opportunities for continuous skill development and education, providing organizations with the tools and resources necessary to navigate evolving technologies, regulatory changes, and diverse societal needs.
- **Democracy Education Resources:** Showcase how resources and tools produced within the Critical ChangeLab project can be utilised by CSOs to foster young people's civic engagement and broader democracy education.

- **Professional Development and Networking:** Emphasize the opportunities for professional development and networking that organizations can access through involvement with the Critical ChangeLab project, enabling them to expand their networks, collaborate with like-minded partners, and stay informed about industry trends.

4.4.4 Channels used for reaching TG4

COMMUNICATION	DISSEMINATION	EXPLOITATION
Website	Direct Outreach	Critical ChangeLab
Social Media	Workshops and focus groups	Youth Mentorship Program
Newsletter	Civil society festivals	Critical ChangeLab Resource Library Critical ChangeLab MOOC

4.5 Target Group 5: Policy and decision makers

This target group consists of policy and institutional decision-makers across a range of areas but predominantly those who engage with policy surrounding education, democratic participation, and young people. The group includes influential individuals from diverse sectors – educational governance, local administrations, national ministries of education, regulators, funding agencies governmental advisers, and policy developers – who have the power to guide legislative and regulatory decisions at both institutional, local, national and supra-national levels.

4.5.1 Audience profile of TG5

Table 13: Audience profile of Target Group 5 (TG5)

INTERESTS	Have a vested interest in shaping policies surrounding education, advancing democratic participation, and enhancing opportunities for young people. Their interests include fostering civic skills among young people, educational systems, and promoting democratic governance.
NEEDS AND PREFERENCES	Their needs revolve around research-based evidence, insights about prevailing educational practices and systems, proactive engagement with respective

	communities, and effective solutions for real-world policy challenges. They prefer evidence-based policy-making and lean towards practices and solutions that uphold democracy, education advancement, and youth participation.
CHANNELS	Communication channels largely utilized by this group are government meetings, policy briefings, seminars, intellectual forums, official communications, white papers, and well-regarded journals.
CHALLENGES	Their challenges lie in balancing diverse interests, keeping pace with technological changes in education, understanding the evolving needs of young people, and ensuring democratic values are upheld in a rapidly changing society.
BEHAVIOUR	Demonstrates responsive, consultative, and introspective behaviour, often seeking to engage key stakeholders in decision-making processes. They are adaptive and willing to innovate within policy frameworks in response to societal and technological changes.
INFLUENCE	Decisions are influenced by multiple factors, including socio-economic trends, research-backed insights, stakeholder perspectives, and the effectiveness of proposed solutions. Moreover, influences can derive from those who advocate for education, democratic values, and youth-oriented policies, both within their network and throughout broader society.

4.5.2 Relationship of TG5 to Critical ChangeLab & Objectives

Connected communication objectives

CO3 DEMONSTRATE IMPACT

CO4 ADVOCATE CHANGE

This group will be targeted through a series of policy outputs undertaken within WP4 that are informed by all the project research and activities. At least 100 policy makers and decision-makers will directly engage with project activities. A minimum of 20 policy-makers will be engaged in Critical Change Lab activities or attend the international policy workshop. Whereas a total of 500 policy-makers will find out about the Critical ChangeLab outputs and outcomes through the project dissemination actions.

4.5.3 Key messages & channels for reaching TG5

Policy and decision-makers are expected to respond to key messages that emphasise the value of the outputs of the Critical ChangeLab in enacting positive social and that supported through documented evidence.

- **Evidence-based Policy:** Emphasize how the outputs and research-based evidence from the Critical ChangeLab project can inform and guide policy decisions, providing policy and decision-makers with valuable insights into prevailing educational practices and effective solutions.
- **Advancing Democratic Participation:** Highlight the importance of fostering civic skills among young people, enhancing educational systems, and promoting democratic governance, showcasing how the Critical ChangeLab project aligns with these goals and offers practical strategies for achieving them.
- **Enhancing Youth Opportunities:** Showcase how the Critical ChangeLab project contributes to enhancing opportunities for young people, providing policy and decision-makers with innovative approaches to addressing the evolving needs of young people and ensuring their active participation in society.
- **Engagement with Stakeholders:** Emphasize the consultative and collaborative approach of the Critical ChangeLab project, showcasing how policy and decision makers can engage with key stakeholders, including educators, community leaders, and especially young people themselves.

4.5.4 Channels used for reaching TG4

COMMUNICATION	DISSEMINATION	EXPLOITATION
Website	Direct Outreach	Policy Publications
Social Media (primarily Paid Ads)	Workshops and focus groups	
Newsletter		

5. Action Plan and Workflow

5.1 Coordinating Communication

AE will be responsible for coordinating the communication of the project, and this will require ensuring there is ongoing clear communication between partners on the status of outputs, how terms are defined, and the messages that the project should share. This is achieved through the following workflows.

Partner communication officers

- Each partner organisation has nominated a person responsible for liaising with AE on actions concerning communication.
- Communication officers will meet monthly to coordinate the communication actions within campaigns.

WP & Deliverable Lead Check-Ins

- AE personnel will occasionally join task-focused group meetings and review the minutes from these meetings. This ensures that the communication strategy aligns with the ongoing activities and outputs of the project.

Editorial and social media templates

- AE will provide editorial and social media templates to ensure a cohesive narrative and a coherent visual presence of the project across all communication partners and campaigns. These templates will be important for the collection of the Critical ChangeLab Stories during each PAR cycle, as well as other blog content.

5.2 Communication Code-of-Conduct

At all times, the Critical ChangeLab project will strive to foster an environment of accessible, responsible, and participatory communication. A Critical ChangeLab Communication Code-of-Conduct will be developed by AE in active consultation with partners. The code-of-conduct will reflect the projects values and share its belief in the power of effective communication to bridge divides, promote understanding, and enable collaboration.

The Code-of-Conduct will address fair, inclusive and diverse communication within the consortium and beyond towards project participants and external stakeholders. The explicit objective of this Code of Conduct is to lower the barriers in accessibility and outreach by equally addressing and bridging cultural differences, barriers stemming from different education & training systems, economic, geographical, or social barriers and those to linked to discrimination.

The Code of Conduct aims to promote fair, inclusive, and diverse communication practices within the consortium and extend these practices towards project participants and external stakeholders. Its explicit objective is to reduce barriers to accessibility and outreach by addressing and bridging cultural differences, as well as barriers arising from varying education and training systems, economic, geographical, social, and discriminatory factors. By implementing this Code of Conduct, the consortium strives to create a communication environment that is accessible and welcoming to all individuals, regardless of background or circumstances.

The first draft of the Code-of-Conduct (Annex 2) was formulated after workshops with the consortium partners and will be further refined by M8.

5.3 Accessible design guidelines

In tandem with the communication code-of-conduct, guidelines for accessible design will be made available to partners and collaborators. Accessible design reflects the values of the project of opening up working processes, criteria, and methodologies to civil society, ensuring transparency and inclusivity. By implementing accessible design principles, the communication plan ensures that the information and content provided can be easily understood and accessed by a wide range of individuals, including those with disabilities or limited access to resources.

Accessible design guidelines will help to address and bridge cultural differences and barriers arising from varying education and training systems, economic, geographical, social, and discriminatory factors. It ensures that all individuals, regardless of their background or circumstances, can equally access and engage with the project's content and activities.

6. Monitoring and Evaluation

As the primary role of the communication strategy is to contribute achieving it's the project objectives, the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation KPIS are closely aligned with the overall project KPIS. AE will therefore work closely alongside the project coordinator (UOULU) in monitoring the project KPIS.

Partners have been provided a dashboard where to log their activities on a regular basis to assist AE in tracking the dissemination, exploitation and communication activities throughout the project and effectively evaluating the performance of the communication plan.

The progress of the activities and the achievement of the KPIS have been reported in the interim project review in M15. Additionally, in the final month of the project, a comprehensive report (D4.7) will be prepared by AE, covering all project communication and dissemination activities. This report will provide an overview of the performance, outcomes, and impact of the communication efforts undertaken by the Critical ChangeLab partners.

The monitoring and evaluation process ensures that the communication activities are effectively reaching the intended audiences and achieving the desired objectives. Any deviations from the planned targets can be identified and necessary measures can be taken to address them. This allows for continuous improvement and optimization of the communication strategy throughout the project lifetime.

7. Conclusion

This document summarizes and revises the Communication Plan for the Critical ChangeLab project that was developed within the set-up Communication Guidelines & Plan for consortium (T4.1). The Communication Plan highlights the strategies and actions designed to effectively disseminate project outcomes, reach target audiences, and generate awareness about the project's goals, objectives. The Plan aims to ensure the flexible utilization of project outputs, aligning with significant needs and optimal opportunities for communication, dissemination, and exploitation.

This deliverable functions as a living document to be utilised by all consortium partners and collaborators. It serves as a roadmap to effectively communicate project activities, outcomes, and approaches to a wide range of stakeholders. The Plan outlines how the communication strategy will support the project in achieving its goals by generating awareness, fostering dialogue, encouraging collaboration and advancing democratic pedagogy in educational settings, and disseminating the knowledge resulted from our research.

While the initial plan remains a point of reference, the current communication plan and guidelines proposes a more targeted, personalised strategy. This strategy has been informed by the learnings from the first year of the project, and the evolving needs of the project as more research and practical tools are published and require a more targeted promotion strategy. The revised communication plan incorporates learnings from the first year and responds to the future needs of the project.

Thus, we depart from the initial plan that focused on online communication campaigns (typically less targeted). Instead, we start by drawing connections between the communication objectives and the tasks and deliverables of the project. As we move forward, we give an overview of the channels we plan to use for the more general communication measures, and for more targeted dissemination and exploitation measures. As we go into the definition of the target groups, beyond defining their profiles (their interests, needs, motivations, etc.) and the key messages, we establish their relations to the objectives of the communication channels, as well as the best channels through which we can reach them.

Clearly drawing a line from the communication objectives to the tasks and deliverables, and then further to the target groups and the channels makes for a more effective strategy that, while it might not yield the highest numbers, will ensure we can reach relevant audiences and clearly communicate the impact our model and methods can have, and advocate for its inclusion in the school curricula both at the policy-maker level and the education professionals level.

As we move into the second part of the project – when more resources are published and the time comes to present the benefits and exploitability of our outputs – the communication measures will be key to formulating coherent and unified narratives and messages, but they will be amplified by the setting in motion of dissemination and exploitations measures and the activation of those channels to promote key outputs of the project.

8. References

Carey, J. M., Clayton, K., Helmke, G., Nyhan, B., Sander, M., & Stokes, S. (2019). Party, policy, democracy and candidate choice in US elections, Bright Line Watch.

Checkoway, B. (2011). What is youth participation?. *Children and youth services review*, 33(2), 340–345.

Cosentino, G. (2020). *Social media and the post-truth world order*. London; Cham: Palgrave Pivot.

Escobar, O. (2017). Pluralism and democratic participation: What kind of citizen are citizens invited to be?. *Contemporary pragmatism*, 14(4), 416–438.

Foa, R. S., & Mounk, Y. (2017). The signs of deconsolidation. *J. Democracy*, 28, 5.

IDEA (2021). *The global state of democracy 2021. Building resilience in a pandemic era*. Stockholm, Sweden: International Institute for

Democracy and Electoral Assistance. https://www.idea.int/gsod/sites/default/files/2021-11/the-global-state-of-democracy-2021_1.pdf

Kirsch, H., & Welzel, C. (2019). Democracy misunderstood: authoritarian notions of democracy around the globe. *Social Forces*, 98(1), 59–92.

König, P. D., Siewert, M. B., & Ackermann, K. (2022). Conceptualizing and measuring citizens' preferences for democracy: Taking stock of three decades of research in a fragmented field. *Comparative Political Studies*, 55(12), 2015–2049.

Krastev, I., & Holmes, S. (2019). *The light that failed: A reckoning*. Penguin UK.

Mos, M. (2020). Ambiguity and interpretive politics in the crisis of European values: Evidence from Hungary. *East European Politics*, 36(2), 267–287.

Mounk, Y. (2018). The people vs. democracy: Why our freedom is in danger and how to save it. In *The People vs. Democracy*. Harvard University Press.

Reynié, D. (2019). *Democracies under Pressure. A Global Survey*, Paris: International Republican Institute/Fondation pour l'innovation politique, www.fondapol.org/en/etudesen/new-global-survey-democracies-under-pressure-volume-i-the-issues/

Runciman, D (2018) *How Democracy Ends*. New York: Basic Books.
Surowiec, P., & Štětka, V. (2020). Introduction: media and illiberal democracy in Central and Eastern Europe. *East European Politics*, 36(1), 1-8.
van Dyk, S. (2022). Post-Truth, the Future of Democracy and the Public Sphere. *Theory, Culture & Society*, 39(4), 37-50.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/02632764221103514>

Warren, M. E. (2002). What can democratic participation mean today?. *Political theory*, 30(5), 677-701.

Wuttke, A., Gavras, K., & Schoen, H. (2022). Have Europeans grown tired of democracy? New evidence from eighteen consolidated democracies, 1981-2018. *British Journal of Political Science*, 52(1), 416-428.

Zilinsky, J. (2019). Democratic deconsolidation revisited: Young Europeans are not dissatisfied with democracy. *Research & Politics*, 6(1), 2053168018814332.

9. Annexes

Annex 1: Critical ChangeLab Visual Identity

Annex 2: Critical ChangeLab Code of Conduct

Annex 3: Possible Communication Campaigns

CRITICAL CHANGE LAB

Deliverable D4.1

Appendix 1: Visual Identity Manual

CRITICAL CHANGE LAB

color palette

RGB 236 99 120
CMYK 0 73 36 0
#EC6378

90% 70% 50% 30% 10%

RGB 76 69 93
CMYK 68 64 34 40
#4C455D

90% 70% 50% 30% 10%

RGB 156 205 209
CMYK 43 5 19 0
#9CCDD1

90% 70% 50% 30% 10%

RGB 152 168 143
CMYK 42 20 44 10
#98A88F

90% 70% 50% 30% 10%

RGB 239 127 79
CMYK 0 60 70 0
#EF7F4F

90% 70% 50% 30% 10%

RGB 220 223 89
CMYK 20 0 75 0
#DCDF59

90% 70% 50% 30% 10%

typography

Poppins

Designed by Indian Type Foundry,
Jonny Pinhorn

fonts.google.com/specimen/Poppins

This font is licensed under the Open Font License.

Poppins Regular

AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIi
JjKkLlMmNnOoPpQqRr
SsTtUuVvWwXxYyZz
1234567890&!:,;.,

Poppins SemiBold

AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIi
JjKkLlMmNnOoPpQqRr
SsTtUuVvWwXxYyZz
1234567890&!:,;.,

Poppins Bold

AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIi
JjKkLlMmNnOoPpQqRr
SsTtUuVvWwXxYyZz
1234567890&!:,;.,

Poppins Italic

AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIi
JjKkLlMmNnOoPpQqRr
SsTtUuVvWwXxYyZz
1234567890&!:,;.,

Poppins SemiBold Italic

AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIi
JjKkLlMmNnOoPpQqRr
SsTtUuVvWwXxYyZz
1234567890&!:,;.,

Poppins Bold Italic

AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIi
JjKkLlMmNnOoPpQqRr
SsTtUuVvWwXxYyZz
1234567890&!:,;.,

logo

Critical Change Lab
three-line logo

black
on light background

white
on dark background

sub-logos

Critical Change Lab
sub-logos

- Education
- Exhibitions
- Podcasts & Publications
- Prototyping
- Conference

black
on light background

sub-logos

Critical Change Lab
sub-logos

- Education
- Exhibitions
- Podcasts & Publications
- Prototyping
- Conference

white
on dark background

CRITICAL
CHANGE LAB
LINZ

CRITICAL
CHANGE LAB
AMSTERDAM

CRITICAL
CHANGE LAB
XXX

CRITICAL
CHANGE LAB
XXX

CRITICAL
CHANGE LAB
XXX

CRITICAL
CHANGE LAB
XXX

logo

Critical Change Lab
single-line logo

black
on light background

white
on dark background

CRITICAL CHANGE LAB

CRITICAL CHANGE LAB

logo

Critical Change Lab
short-form logo

black
on light background

white
on dark background

The logo is identical to the one above, but rendered in white against a dark purple background.

website

Critical Change Lab
website

banner
buttons

icons

Critical Change Lab
icons / graphic elements

black
on light background

white
on dark background

CRITICAL CHANGE LAB

Deliverable D4.1

Appendix 2: Critical ChangeLab Communication Code-of-Conduct v1.0

Critical ChangeLab

Communication Code-of-Conduct

At all times, we strive to foster an environment of accessible, responsible, and participatory communication. We believe in the power of effective communication to bridge divides, promote understanding, and enable collaboration. To ensure an inclusive and respectful atmosphere, we adhere to the following code of conduct:

Respect and Inclusivity:

- Treat all individuals with respect, dignity, and fairness, irrespective of their background, identity, or beliefs.
- Foster an inclusive environment where everyone feels valued and heard, regardless of their abilities, language, or communication preferences.
- Be mindful of potential power imbalances and actively work to give space to marginalized voices.

Clear and Accessible Communication:

- Strive for clarity and simplicity in communication, using plain language and avoiding jargon or technical terms whenever possible.
- Provide appropriate context and explanations to ensure understanding by all participants, including those with diverse backgrounds and levels of expertise.
- Utilize diverse communication methods and channels to accommodate different preferences and ensure accessibility for individuals with disabilities.

Responsible and Ethical Engagement:

- Be accountable for the accuracy and validity of the information we share, striving to verify facts and sources before dissemination.
- Refrain from spreading misinformation, rumors, or harmful content that may undermine trust or mislead others.
- Respect intellectual property rights, giving proper credit for ideas, quotes, or references used in communication.

Active Listening and Empathy:

- Practice active listening, allowing others to express their thoughts and opinions without interruption or judgement.
- Show empathy and understanding towards different perspectives, valuing diverse viewpoints as opportunities for growth and learning.
- Engage in constructive dialogue, asking questions for clarification and seeking common ground to foster collaboration.

Authentic and Consistent Communication:

- Strive for transparency and authenticity in our communication, promoting honest and genuine interactions.
- Maintain consistency in our messaging, ensuring that it aligns with our values and organizational goals.
- Respond promptly and professionally to inquiries, acknowledging the importance of timely and respectful communication.

By adhering to this Communication Code-of-Conduct, we aim to create an environment that encourages equitable participation, responsible dialogue, and effective collaboration. Together, we can foster accessible, responsible, and participatory communication for the benefit of all.

CRITICAL CHANGE LAB

Deliverable D4.1

Appendix 3: Possible Communication Campaigns

Annex 3: Possible Communication Campaigns

The outlined campaigns in this Communication Plan are not definitive and will adapt to the activities of the Critical ChangeLab project as necessary. Keeping this flexibility in mind, the following campaigns will establish the overarching framework of the communication activities of the project, without limiting us in coming up with more suitable campaigns, activity or even a strategy that can better serve the communication, dissemination and exploitation of the outputs.

Table 1: Suggested Timeline of Communication Campaigns

	Month	Campaign	Dependencies	Target Group	Partners
Y 1	7	Project Launch	MS1, MS2, D4.1	All	AE / All
	8	Partner Introductions	MS1, D4.1	All	AE / All
	9	Call to Collaborate in Critical ChangeLabs	MS2, D4.1	TG2, TG4	AE / All
	10	Democracy Health Index Participation Launch	MS3, D1.1	TG1, TG2	AE / All
	11	Everyday democracy in formal and non-formal education institutions	D1.2	TG1, TG2	ISRZ / AE
Y 2	13	Youth perspectives on everyday democracy in education	D1.3	All	ISRZ / All
	14	Introducing Critical ChangeLab Framework and Toolkit	MS5, D1.4	TG1, TG2	UOULU / AE
	15	Making policy for everyday democracy in education	D4.2	TG5	ISRZ / ALTEREURO
	16	Critical ChangeLab Stories (PAR Cycle 1)	MS5, D1.4	All	AE / All
	22	Critical ChangeLab Stories (PAR Cycle 2)	D2.1	All	AE / All
	23	Voices of Youth Campaign	D4.4	All	AE
Y 3	24	Critical ChangeLab MOOC Launch	D4.3	TG2, TG3	ALTEEURO / AE
	27	Critical ChangeLab Stories (Cycle 3)	D2.2	All	AE / All
	31	Youth Assembly Stories	D5.1	All	AE
	32	Critical ChangeLab Ideas for Practice	D3.1	TG1, TG2, TG4, TG5	UB / ALTEREURO
	32	Critical ChangeLab Ideas for Policy	D4.5, D4.6	TG5	UB / ALTEREURO
	32	Critical ChangeLab Educators' Handbook	D2.3	TG1, TG2, TG4	WAAG / AE

33	Critical ChangeLab Model for Democratic Pedagogy: Developing 21st Century Skills for Democratic Participation	D3.2	TG1, TG2, TG4	UOULU / AE
35	Mapping Impact	D3.3, D3.4, D4.7	All	TCD, UB, AE

1.1 Project Launch

Estimated timeframe of campaign: M7

The communication campaign for launching the project aims to effectively introduce the Critical ChangeLab project to its target audiences and generate awareness and engagement. It involves a variety of communication measures targeted at specific audiences, including building media capabilities, establishing online and social media platforms, and organizing events with public engagement in various countries.

Online communication plays a significant role in the campaign, providing a practical gateway for reaching a wide range of audiences. A website will host a public/media-oriented version of the project contents, including short biographies of the project participants and institutions. The existing social media channels of the consortium will be leveraged to spread and accelerate communication from the project's website.

Overall, the communication campaign aims to create a first contact for audiences with the project's societal or scientific goals and outcomes. It focuses on conveying accurate scientific information in a way that is accessible to the general audience. The objective is to reach a large number of citizens through various communication activities, ensuring transparency of work and demonstrating the open and democratic nature of the project's working process.

Dependencies	Partner Contributions
This campaign is dependent on the successful delivery of the project website and the visual guidelines.	Partners will contribute by utilising their existing social media channels to communicate the launch of the project and direct their existing audiences to the Critical ChangeLab project. Partners will also adapt the press release launching the project, so it is suitable to the existing press contacts of their individual organisations.

1.1 Partner Introductions

Estimated timeframe of campaign: M8

The purpose of this campaign is to introduce all the participating partner organisations. It will highlight the diversity of communities, approaches, and expertise within each organisation. The campaign will consist of interviews with representatives of the organisations, exploring how the goals of the project align with each of the organisation’s goals, and reflecting on previous activities and projects that examined issues or methods that will be further developed within Critical ChangeLab.

Dependencies	Partner Contributions
This campaign will be largely dependent on the accessibility, availability, and engagement of the consortium partners.	Each partner will be requested to nominate an individual to participate in an interview undertaken by AE and to share the published interviews on their social media channels.

1.2 Call to Collaborate in Critical ChangeLabs

Estimated timeframe of campaign: M9

This campaign follows the more general introductions provided within the first two campaigns, with more specific details on the Critical ChangeLabs. The aim of this campaign is to support consortium partners and associated partners in engaging stakeholders to collaborate with the Critical ChangeLabs, and it will focus on providing contextual information to potential collaborators.

Dependencies	Partner Contributions
This campaign is dependent on Milestone 2 - Definition of the Critical Literacies Framework (MS2) and the development of the Critical Literacies Framework that will be important for defining the terms that describe the Critical ChangeLabs. The campaign is also highly dependent on the work that has been done at this stage toward D1.4 – Critical ChangeLab Model: Framework and Toolkit and the	All partners will be involved in this campaign as it will have an impact on how they will run Critical ChangeLabs. The campaign will be informed by what is the most important information concerning the Critical ChangeLabs they will implement. AE will work actively with UOULU on how the Critical ChangeLabs should be described at this early stage to support the recruitment of collaborators. TCD will also support this process, by ensuring that the communication

defining of the Critical ChangeLab Model: Framework and Toolkit. aligns with the knowledge from Milestone 2 – Definition of the Critical Literacies Framework (MS2)

1.3 Democracy Index Participation Launch

Estimated timeframe of campaign: M10

The objective of this campaign is to assist consortium partners in actively involving educational institutions in the administration of the Democracy Health Index questionnaire. The outreach to and engagement of educational partners will be managed directly by the partners themselves in a way that is relevant to each national context. This campaign will be focused on providing information about the Democracy Health Index, explaining the purpose of the research is its importance for the broader goals of the project.

Dependencies	Partner Contributions
This campaign is dependent on the development of the Democracy Health Index, the timeline of its implementation, and the tools it will use to distribute the questionnaires and collect the data.	ISRZ who is responsive for the Democracy Health Index (DHI) will work with AE in framing how this campaign can best support the successful delivery of the DHI.

1.4 Everyday democracy in formal and non-formal education institutions

Estimated timeframe of campaign: M11

This campaign will provide a snapshot and tell a story the current state of everyday democracy in formal and non-formal education institutions. It will focus on institutional perspectives and will be informed by the quantitative research undertaken through the Democracy Health Index and the qualitative research case undertaken within D1.2 – Everyday democracy in formal and non-formal education institutions and its corresponding case studies.

Dependencies	Partner Contributions
This campaign is dependent on the successful completion of the research undertaken within D1.1 and D1.2.	ISRZ will work closely with AE, and with the input from all partners, to work out the best way to communicate the research and how it can engage non-scientific audiences.

1.5 Youth perspectives on everyday democracy in education
Estimated timeframe of campaign: M13

This campaign follows on from the previous campaign that was informed by D1.1 – Instrument: Democracy Health Questionnaire and Index and D1.2 – Everyday democracy in formal and non-formal education institutions, however this campaign will highlight the perspectives of young people and their experiences of everyday democracy in education.

Dependencies	Partner Contributions
This campaign is also dependent on the successful completion of the research undertaken within D1.1 – Instrument: Democracy Health Questionnaire and Index and D1.2 – Everyday democracy in formal and non-formal education institutions.	ISRZ will work closely with AE work out the best way to communicate the research and how it can engage non-scientific audiences. Partners will also have important responsibility during this campaign to make sure how the perspectives of young people are communicated are considerate to the communities that they worked with while undertaking the case studies.

1.6 Introducing Critical ChangeLab Framework and Toolkit
Estimated timeframe of campaign: M14

This campaign will introduce in more detail the Critical ChangeLabs and communicate the D1.4 – Critical ChangeLab Model: Framework and Toolkit. It will communicate Critical ChangeLab methods and a variety of flexible tools.

This campaign will be an important milestone in terms of communication, as it will be an opportunity to clarify the Critical ChangeLabs within a more practical and action-based context and will be supported by educational resources that will be made openly available for educators to utilise.

Dependencies	Partner Contributions
This campaign is dependent on the successful completion of D1.4 – Critical ChangeLab Model: Framework and Toolkit.	UOULU will work closely with AE to ensure the successful communication of this campaign.

1.7 Making policy for everyday democracy in education

Estimated timeframe of campaign: M15

This campaign will accompany the first policy publication produced within Critical ChangeLab with D4.2 – Policy Brief 1. Informed by the outputs of WP4 Map & Design, the publication focuses on the policy implications a Critical ChangeLab Model for Democratic Pedagogy could have. The campaign itself will focus more broadly on the relationship of policy to democracy education while also working to disseminate the policy publication that will be published in the Resource Library.

Dependencies	Partner Contributions
This campaign is dependent on successful completion of D4.2 – Policy Brief 1.	AE will work alongside ALTEREURO who is leading the policy outputs of WP4, and in consultation with ISRZ who is responsible for D4.2 in creating the messaging for this campaign.

1.8 Critical ChangeLab Stories (PAR Cycles 1-3)

Estimated timeframe of campaign: M16, M22, M29

This campaign will give an account of the Critical ChangeLabs conducted by all partners and will map the evolution of the methodology from the first to the last PAR Cycle.

Dependencies	Partner Contributions
These campaigns are dependent on the successful implementation of the Critical ChangeLabs by all partner for each cycle. The success of the campaign is also dependent on the willing and enthusiastic participation from learners and educators involved in the labs in contributing to communicating their experience.	All partners implementing Critical ChangeLabs will be responsible for independently producing the content documenting their Labs each cycle.

1.9 Youth Assembly Stories

Estimated timeframe of campaign: M28

This campaign will coincide with an in-person meeting of the Critical ChangeLab Youth Assembly that will take place at the Ars Electronica Festival in 2025. It will introduce each of the 10 members of the Youth Assembly, their motivation for getting involved with Critical

Changelab and reflect more broadly on their experiences of and aspirations for democracy in Europe.

Dependencies	Partner Contributions
This campaign is dependent on the establishment of the Youth Assembly and their agreement to participate in the communication campaign.	All partners will be asked to facilitate between their respective national members of the Youth Assemble and AE.

1.10 Voices of Youth

Estimated timeframe of campaign: M23

The Voice of Youth video campaign will consist of a series of vlogs and video statements from 40 young people on their views for a sustainable future. The young people invited to contribute to the Voices of Youth campaign will be those who have taken part in the Critical ChangeLabs, and those that received mentoring. They belong to historically underrepresented groups in formal European democratic processes.

The campaign will explore the conceptualisation of young people as citizens and agents and what implications this has on the required competences for democratic culture. The campaign will focus on making sure the voice of young people themselves are not only heard, but actively listened to, when strategies, policies, approaches and pedagogies are made about or for them.

The videos will be published on Youtube, with corresponding blog articles, and shared across partner social media channels. The videos produced within this campaign will also provide a source of content that could be used for presentation at festivals and conferences that feature outputs or participation from the Critical ChangeLab project.

Dependencies	Partner Contributions
This campaign is dependent on the implementation of first PAR cycle of Critical ChangeLabs, and the establishment of the mentoring program.	AE will lead the Voice of Youth. All partners will actively contribute to produce the videos with the young people participating in the project activities. ALTEREURO will also be closely involved as the responsible partner for the Youth Mentoring Program.

1.11 Critical ChangeLab MOOC Launch

Estimated timeframe of campaign: M24

This campaign will introduce and promote the Critical ChangeLab MOOC and will be designed with EUROALTER who is responsible for Deliverable D4.3 – Critical ChangeLab Model of Democratic Pedagogy MOOC.

The campaign will highlight the key benefits and impact of the MOOC, such as strengthening democracy in education, advancing global citizenship education, promoting collaborations between educational institutions and CSOs/industry, and raising awareness about the importance of cultivating democracy in daily practices.

The MOOC campaign will highlight the unique innovations and applicability of the Critical ChangeLab Model as demonstrated in the previous labs and supported by the research and educational resources published by the project. The MOOC campaign will aim to include testimonials from previous participants of the Critical ChangeLabs and/or any of the educators, researchers and other experts that have collaborated with the Critical ChangeLabs.

Given its substantial enrolment/use target, this campaign is foreseen to use paid ads, alongside the usual online channels. Targeted online advertising campaigns would take place on social media platforms (LinkedIn) where it can reach interested audiences.

This campaign will use the newsletter specifically set up for the Critical ChangeLab project but will also engage the consortium partners independent organisational mailing lists.

Moreover, the campaign will develop an email marketing strategy that reaches out to educators, teacher education students in Europe, and also other potential participants outside of Europe who may be interested in the MOOC.

Dependencies	Partner Contributions
This campaign is dependent on deliver of D4.3 – Critical ChangeLab Model of Democratic Pedagogy MOOC and Milestone 6 – Critical ChangeLab MOOC (MS6) and the completion of the MOOC and it successfully going live online.	All partners will work together to promote the MOOC across their organisation’s networks.

1.12 Critical ChangeLab’s Ideas for Practice

Estimated timeframe of campaign: M30

This campaign is focused on communicating the recommendations for practice developed within D3.1 – Critical ChangeLab process and recommendations for practice (informed by the evaluation of the activities). The campaign will also use the publication of these recommendations to further promote the Critical ChangeLab Model, and the educational resources that have been previously made available. The goal of the campaign is to succinctly summarise the recommendations for practice and contribute to fostering interest in the framework and tool kits.

Dependencies	Partner Contributions
The campaign is dependent on the successful completion of D3.1	AE will work alongside ALTEREURO and UB, the partner responsible for D3.1, to summarise and communicate the Recommendations for Practice.

1.13 Critical ChangeLab’s Ideas for Policy

Estimated timeframe of campaign: M31

This campaign will communicate the concluding report on policy recommendations published within D4.6 Policy recommendations on citizenship education for sustainable European democracy. This final campaign focused on policy will also draw on all the policy briefs published during the project, and the online communication will highlight the availability of each of these reports within the Critical ChangeLab Resource Library.

The campaign will have the goal of demonstrating the impact of the project by showcasing the Critical ChangeLab’s collection of evidence-based innovations, policies and policy recommendations, as well as institutional frameworks that expand political participation, social dialogue, civic engagement, gender equality and inclusiveness.

Dependencies	Partner Contributions
This campaign is dependent on the completion of D4.6 Policy recommendations on citizenship education for sustainable European democracy.	AE will work with WP4 leader and author of D4.6 ALTEREURO, with contributions from all the consortium partners that authored policy briefs and recommendations throughout the project.

1.14 Critical ChangeLab Educators’ Handbook

Estimated timeframe of campaign: M32

This campaign will further contribute to the communication objective of multiplying knowledge, by promoting the publication of the Critical Change Lab Educators’ Handbook in the Resource Library that will support educators and their education communities to adopt the Model.

Dependencies	Partner Contributions
This campaign is dependent on the successful publication of D2.3 – Critical ChangeLab Educators’ Handbook.	Waag will lead the development and dissemination of the handbook, with the support of AE and partners, and with key contributions from TCD and UOULU.

1.15 The Critical ChangeLab Model

Estimated timeframe of campaign: M33

This campaign will outline and clearly communicate what is effectively the most significant output of the project, the **Critical ChangeLab Model** for Democratic Pedagogy: Developing 21st Century Skills for Democratic Participation. The campaign will be focused on describing what this model is, and how it has been informed by all the activities and outputs undertaken in the project.

Dependencies	Partner Contributions
This campaign is dependent on the successful completion of deliverable D3.2 – Critical ChangeLab Model for Democratic Pedagogy: Developing 21 st Century Skills for Democratic Participation.	UOULU as the lead of the deliverable and coordinator of the project will play a significant role in developing this communication campaign with AE. All partners will also expect to play an active role in contributing to this campaign.

1.16 Mapping Impact

Estimated timeframe of campaign: M35

This campaign is informed by the final deliverables of the project focused on evaluating the project. This campaign will review everything that has occurred over the three years of the

project's duration, supported by evidence provided through the evaluation of the project in D3.3 - Critical ChangeLab impact evaluation.

Dependencies	Partner Contributions
<p>This campaign is dependent on completion of D3.3 - Critical ChangeLab impact evaluation, D3.4 - Policy recommendations based on the socio-economic evaluation of the Critical ChangeLab Model, and D4.7 - Report on all project communication and dissemination activities, that will be delivered in the final stages of the project.</p>	<p>As a final campaign, all partners will be expected to be involved in this campaign.</p>

